

ICAENS 2022 PROGRAM

Session 1.1		20 JULY 2022 10:00-11:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
A Review of Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV): Its Impact and Challenges	Muhammad Baballe Ahmad, Mukhtar Ibrahim Bello, Adamu Alkali Umar, Zainab Abdulkadir, Abubakar Sadiq Muhammad and Fatima Abubakar Usman	Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria	Submission 0665
On the decay of the energy for a quasilinear hyperbolic wave equation with source terms.	Abir Bounaama	Algeria	Submission 1153
Design and Implementation of the hand Pick and Place Cobots' Arms for	Muhammad Baballe Ahmad, Mukhtar Ibrahim Bello, Abubakar Sadiq Muhammad, Abubakar Abdullahi Umar, Fatima Abubakar Usman and Abdulmuhamin Muhammad	Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria	Submission 1254
Distributional solution for non-linear fractional problem involving the distributional Riesz gradient	Chaima Saadi and Hakim Lakhel	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 9466
Pauli Oscillator under Magnetic Field in Noncommutative Anti-deSitter Space	Lakhdar Sek, Mokhtar Falek and Mustafa Mourni	Algeria	Submission 9594

Session 1.2		20 JULY 2022 10:00-11:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Challenges in Managing Multicultural Workforce in Construction Projects	Ali Kara, Larno Meyer and Olcay Genç	Qatar, Qatar, Turkey	Submission 6630
A Review Study on the Effects of Dimethyl Ether on CO Emissions in Diesel Engines	İsmet Sezer	Turkey	Submission 8839
A Review Study on the Effects of Dimethyl Ether on HC Emissions in Diesel Engines	İsmet Sezer	Turkey	Submission 2971
Passive Intermodulation Measurement System	Hüseyin Anıktar	Turkey	Submission 7489
Study for a Nickel-Based Alloy Using One of the Recent Technologies for Applications	Murat Işık	Turkey	Submission 4795
Detection of Covid 19 Disease with Machine Learning Methods	Esat Ayaz and Reyat Yılmaz	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1969

Session 1.3		20 JULY 2022 11:00-12:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Automatic Water Level Indicator: A Review	Muhammad Ahmad Baballe, Abubakar Sadiq Muhammad, Mukhtar Ibrahim Bello, Adamu Alkali Umar, Fatihu Muhammad and Abdulmuhamin Muhammad	Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria	Submission 1863
Radio Resource Control Inactive State in 5G: Survey and Challenges	Agburu Ahiny'Ohe Ogah Adikpe, Abdoulie Momodou Sunkary Tekanyi and Abdulmalik Shehu Yaro	Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria	Submission 0362
Efficient Sol-gel Nanocomposite TiO ₂ -clay in Photodegradation of Phenol: Comparison to Lab-made and Commercial Photocatalysts	Abdelali El Gaidoumi, Karim Tanji, Amal Loqman, Youssef Fahoul, Abdellah Arrahli, Abdelaziz Dra and Abdelhak Kherbeche	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 5202
Sol-gel fluorinated TiO ₂ - clay nanocomposite: study of fluor-titanium interaction on the photodegradation of phenol	Abdelali El Gaidoumi, Karim Tanji, Youssef Fahoul, Elmustafa Iboustaten, Morad Zouheir and Abdelhak Kherbeche	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 6697
p(.)-Harmonic Maps	Bouchra Merdji	Algeria	Submission 7518

Session 1.4		20 JULY 2022 11:00-12:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Farklı Hammaddelerden Üretilen Biyodizel Yakıtlarının Yağ Asidi İçerikleri Bakımından Karşılaştırılması	Fevzi Yaşar and Hüseyin Şanlı	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 6283
Nanopartikül Katkısı ile Yapıştırma Bağlantılarının Korozif Ortamlardaki Davranışının Geliştirilmesi	Yasemin Korkmaz and Kürşat Gültekin	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 3706
Effects of process control agents in waste Ti6Al4V chips via using ball milling	Bayram Ünal, Muhammed İhsan Özgün, Ahmet Burçin Batıbay, Hakan Burak Karadağ and Yasin Ramazan Eker	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 7931
An Experimental Study on the Mechanical Performance of Nanostructures-Reinforced Structural Adhesively Bonded AA2024-T3 Joints in Seawater Medium	Yasemin Korkmaz and Kürşat Gültekin	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 5495
Epigenetic mechanisms involved in regulation of STEAP1 gene expression in prostate cancer cells	Soumaya Menadi and Ercan Cacan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 4057
Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System for Determination of Risk Levels and Intervention in Forest Fires	Ahmet Şahiner, Muhammad Wasim Awan and Halil İbrahim Gökdoğan	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 7969

Session 1.5		20 JULY 2022 13:00-14:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Global stability of an SIS and an SEIR differential-difference system with age-structured protection phase	Hanene Meghelli and Abdennasser Chekroun	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7030
The influence of calcination temperature on structural and photocatalytic activity of zinc oxide nanoparticles synthesized by Green method	Mohamed Ait Oumeraci, Tarek Berrama, Hayet Tizi and Feriel Sahoui	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 8086
Existence and uniqueness results of an iterative Mackey-Glass model of hematopoiesis	Marwa Khemis, Ahlème Bouakkaz and Rabah Khemis	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 9445
Implementation of System Pharmacology and Molecular Docking Approaches to Explore Active Compounds and Mechanism of Ocimum Sanctum against Tuberculosis	Sana Tabassum, Hafiz Rameez Khalid, Sidra Aslam, Usman Ali Ashfaq, Waqar Ul Haq, Abdulrhman Alshammari, Metab Alharbi, Muhammad Shahid Riaz Rajoka and Mohsin Khurshid	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, UAE, UAE, Japan, Pakistan	Submission 0152
Evaluation of the antioxidant activity of Rosmarinus officinalis essential oils harvested from north of Algeria	Feriel Sahoui, Tarek Ibn Ziad Berrama and Mohamed Ait Oumeraci	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2831

Session 1.6		20 JULY 2022 13:00-14:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Doğa Tabanlı Çözüm Uygulamalarının Evsel Atık Su Yönetimi Çerçevesinde Türkiye için Avantajları	Hasan Volkan Oral and Seyithan Alagöz	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 6109
Fırçasız DC Motor Sürücülerinde Kullanılan Si ve SiC Mosfet Kıyaslanması	Erkan Sevim and Emrah Çetin	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 7998
Influence of Polymer Solution Properties on the Electrospinning of Halochromic Dye Added PAN Nanofibers	Nihal Güçlü, Sebnem Düzyer Gebizli and Mehmet Orhan	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 8315
Process Hazard Analysis and Safe Process Design for the Prevention of Process Accidents in Vertical Solid Fuel Mixers	Oğuzcan Taşdemir and Saliha Çetinyokuş	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 3873
Atıksularda Asimile Edilebilir Organik Karbon Giderimi	Arzu Teksoy and İzel Kenan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 5868
AA Ev Yüklerini Besleyen Fotovoltaik / Batarya Sisteminin MATLAB/SIMULINK Modeli ve Simülasyonu	Furkan Muhammed Kirikci, Miraç Öztürk and Hakan Kahveci	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 0335

Session 1.7		20 JULY 2022 14:00-15:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
The effect of gold nanoparticles on detection of SARS-CoV-2: An overview study on particle size and concentration	Nagihan Emeksiz and Selma Erat	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 6247
Targeting the immune checkpoint VISTA and TLR4 signaling pathway inhibits the proliferation of human pancreatic cancer	Kübra Sena Baş Topcu, Emine Nedime Korucu, Esmâ Menevşe, Nadir Koçak and Tuğçe Duran	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 6875
MediaPipe Hands Algoritması Kullanarak El Rehabilitasyonuna Yönelik Bir Teletıp Uygulaması	Serhan Ayberk Kılıç and Kasım Serbest	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 8735
Elektrikli Otomobiller ve Demokratik Normlar	Ahmet Serdar Güldibi	Turkey	Submission 8361
Detection of Parkinson's Disease from EEG Signals Using Multi-Fractal Analysis and Machine Learning	Hanife Göker	Turkey	Submission 4580
A Forecasting System for Carbon Dioxide Emissions	Seval Ene Yalçın	Turkey	Submission 0962

Session 1.8		20 JULY 2022 14:00-15:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Effect of NaBH ₄ concentration on hardness and microstructural properties of electroless deposited St-37 steel	Yasin Yılmaz, Hatem Akbulut and Mehmet Uysal	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 7570
Cıva Kloridin Ratların Karaciğer Dokusunda Oluşturduğu Histopatolojik Etki Üzerine Mirisetinin Koruyucu Rolü	Emine Doğan and Filiz Demir	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 9801
Static Analysis Investigation of an Example of EMU Bogie Frame	Mert Safak Tunalıoğlu and Recep Uygun	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 8980
Designing Sustainable Supportive Composite Structures with Hemp and Cotton Fibers	Sena Cimilli Duru, Hande Sezgin and Cevza Candan	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 2313
Kripto Para Piyasa Değeri Tahmini için Özellik Tabanlı LSTM ve ARIMA Karşılaştırması	Mert Ali Canitez and Serkan Savaş	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 5291

Session 1.9		20 JULY 2022 15:00-16:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
UWB TOA Estimation for Multiple Targets Based on Singular Value Decomposition Combined With an Iterative Threshold Crossing Algorithm	Ibrahim Yassine Nouali, Zohra Slimane and Abdelhafid Abdelmalek	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1813
Investigation of the Effect of High Level Modulations on the Performance of OFDM-IM Systems over Weibull and Nakagami-m Fading Channels	Senem Conger, Busra Ceniklioglu and Ibrahim Develi	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 5598
Gıda Güvenliđi Riskleri Bakımından Yöresel Pişirme Yöntemleri	İsmet Kutay Sırkılı and Hasan Hüseyin Kara	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 0227
Bartın Kentinde Engelli Dostu Çözümler	Çağla Üstündağ and Mustafa Artar	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1324
NiTi Alaşımına Uygulanan Farklı Sıcaklıklardaki Haddeleme İşlemlerinin Metalografik İncelenmesi	Sinan Aksöz, Nimet Kardeş Sever, Rıdvan Arslan, Ahmet Semih Kışla, Yavuz Kaplan and Bülent Bostan	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 8873

Session 1.10		20 JULY 2022 15:00-16:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Effects of Heat Treatment and on Magnetic Properties of NdFeB Based Permanent Magnet Alloys	Muhammed Fatih Kılıçaslan, Yasin Yılmaz and Bekir Akgul	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 0238
Developing a Computational QSAR Model for Drug Excretion in Breastmilk During the Lactation Period	Feyza Kelleci Çelik and Gül Karaduman	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 3280
Akkermansia muciniphila as a new generation probiotic	Hümeyra İspirli and Enes Dertli	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 9075
Crashworthiness Optimization for Bumper System by Using Stochastic Methods and Neuro Regression Analysis	Hülya Kaplan, Melih Savran and Nilay Küçükdoğan	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 2485
Phytonemus pallidus fragariae (Acari: Tarsonemidae) and its damage symptoms on strawberry plants	Mete Soysal and Rana Akyazı	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 2045
Design and Simulation of Equal Wilkinson Power Divider	İremnur Duru	Turkey	Submission 5159

Session 2.1		21 JULY 2022 09:00-10:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Prebiotic Effects of <i>Salvia fruticosa</i> Mill. and <i>Salvia huberi</i> Hedge water extracts	Mevlüde Nur Topal, Betül Aydın, Murat Koç and Leyla Açık	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 5981
Yerel ürünlerin tüketiciler tarafından tercihi ve sürdürülebilirliğine etkili olan faktörlerinin analizi; Konya ili örneği	Cennet Oğuz and Hatice Kutlu	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 0411
DESIGN OF NEW PEDICLE SCREW AND BIOMECHANICAL EVALUATION USING FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS	Zeliha Coşkun and Talip Çelik	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1446
Adsorptive removal of Mn(II) by natural montmorillonite clay	Fatih Sayın	Turkey	Submission 6747
Turkey's Natural Gas Consumption	Şengül Güven	Turkey	Submission 2582
Special Connections on Pure Metric f-Kählerian Manifolds	Sibel Turanlı	Turkey	mail submission 15

Session 2.2		21 JULY 2022 09:00-10:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Petrol Tankeri Seçim Problemine Yönelik Bir ÇKKV Çerçevesi	Ertuğrul Ayyıldız	Turkey	Submission 6749
A Simulation Study on GaAs Heterojunction through Designing Photodetectors and-or Solar Cells	Ahmet Tuna, Serap Yiğit Gezgin, Yasemin Gündoğdu and Hamdi Şükür Kılıç	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1450
Elektrikli Araçlar (EV) Lityum İyon Batarya Paketinin Konektör Değişimine Bağlı Termal Analizi	Mehmet Çelik, İlhan Kaan Özçetin and İlayda Çınar	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 7793
Fungal cells immobilized on an agricultural waste biomass for the biosorptive treatment of copper pollution	Sema Çelik	Turkey	Submission 1511
KIRSAL KADINLARIN GIDA GÜVENLİĞİ KONUSUNDA TUTUM VE DAVRANIŞLARININ BELİRLENMESİNİ ETKİLEYEN FAKTÖRLERİN ANALİZİ: HÜYÜK İLÇESİ ÖRNEĞİ KONYA, TÜRKİYE	Nur Meraklı Yaman, Cennet OĞUZ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 3986
Cytotoxic Effect of Origanum munzurensis on Prostate Cancer Cell Line	Şeyma Gülnaz Yarıllar, Birgül Mazmancı and Erdal Yabalak	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 4768

Session 2.3		21 JULY 2022 10:00-11:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Design And Analysis Of A Connecting Rod Of Vehicles	Muammer Dursun and Okan Gül	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 7779
Wing Design and Analysis of Fixed Wing Male UAV (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle)	Tarık Buğra Demirel and Okan Gül	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 8298
Shock Load Damping Analysis Using A Vibration Shock Damping Element On Military Ship	Kadir Şentürk and Okan Gül	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 8561
Static Structural Analysis of a Skateboard with Different Deck Thicknesses	Umut Deniz Çaylak and Okan Gül	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 5786
Design And Stress Analysis Of Universal Jack For Automobiles And Light Commercial Vehicles	Furkan Zorlu, Burak İpek and Okan Gül	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 4620
Design and Analysis of An Automobile Stabilizer Bar	Berkay Mendi and Okan Gül	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 0154

Session 2.4		21 JULY 2022 10:00-11:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Electro-elastic problem with adhesion and friction between two bodies	Laldja Benziane and Nemira Lebri	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 0702
Thermo- electro-viscoelastic materials	Aziza Bachmar	Algeria	Submission 0935
lipase catalysed esterification of cellulose nanocrystals with lactic acid	Nacera Leila Belkhir, Mohammed Amin Bezzakhami, Amina Mostfai, Amine Harrane and Mahmoud Belalia	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 0958
Modeling, analysis of NMR, UV-Vis and MS spectra for characterization the compound Narcissin	Rahim Oumelkheir	Algeria	Submission 1077
Intelligent System for the Supervision and Control of a Neonatal Incubator based on Internet of Things	Mohamed Amine Bailiche, Mounir Bouhedda, Yasmine Alikacem and Ikram Benyahia	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1326
Infeasible interior-point point method for solving linear programming problems	Derbal Louiza	Algeria	Submission 1552
Liquid Chromatographic Chiral Separation, Absolute Configuration Assignment and Molecular Docking of Some Antibiotics on Different Polysaccharides Chiral Stationary Phases	Mohamed Nadjib Rebizi	Algeria	Submission 1651
A reliable analytical technique for fractional Newell-Whitehead-Segel equation within Caputo fractional derivative operator	Ali Khalouta	Algeria	Submission 1722
Calculation of Thermal Conductivity of Materials using Einstein-Debye Method	Elif Somuncu	Turkey	Submission 9070
A SIMPLIFIED TRAFFIC SIGN DETECTION AND RECOGNITION SYSTEM USING CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS	Abubakar Sadiq Muhammad and Fahad Abdu Jibrin	Nigeria, Nigeria	Submission 2314

Session 2.5		21 JULY 2022 10:00-11:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Numerical Analysis of Moments of Collision-Induced Scattering with Exp-6 Potential	Elif Somuncu	Turkey	Submission 9243
Enhancement in Splitting Energy Absorption of Concrete with Sisal Fibers for Bridge Girder	Muhammad Abrar, Zain Ul Abideen and Blawal Hasan	Pakistan, pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 2782
bioactivity and corrosion behavior of biomaterials for orthopedic prostheses in SBF solution	Boudjeda Karima and Beliardouh Nasser	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2808
Valorization of low cost biosorbent for heavy metals removal from wastewater	Assia Maazouzi, Nour El Houda Larbi, Hakim Aguedal, Djilali Redha Merouani and Amine Khelifa	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2641
Numerical development of thermal deformation response of building element using rheological model	Nefissa Belkacem and Farid Bouziadi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 3356
Effect on Microwave Radiation Application as Pretreatment on Some Quality Properties of Minced Beef	Süleyman Gökmen	Turkey	Submission 3624
A dynamic frictional contact problem with normal damped response for viscoelastic material with long term-memory	Imane Ouakil, Benyattou Benabderrahmane and Yamna Boukhatem	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 4271
Thermal and optical characterization of an innovative doped PCM for building thermal insulation	Maifi Lyes, Agroui Kamel, Hioual Ouided, Chari Abdelhamid and Kerbache Tahar	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 4429
Effects of Neutral Collisions and Finite Electron Inertia on Longitudinal Jeans-gravitational Instability of Two-component Radiative Plasma in ISM	Dr. Sachin Kaothekar, Sarvesh Mishra and Dr. Sushil Phadke	India, India, India	Submission 4792
A numerical investigation on Electromagnetohydrodynamic flow transport in porous microchannel with wavy walls	Amalendu Rana	India	Submission 4840

Session 2.6		21 JULY 2022 10:00-11:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Detection of Pancreatitis Disease with Convolutional Deep Learning Networks	Sercan Yalçın	Turkey	Submission 4916
Enhanced Protection by STF Treated Foams	Selim Gürgen	Turkey	Submission 4935
Discovering the presence and reproduction of bacteria in water	Dekhili Nourelhouda and Dekhili Meriem	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 5412
Biological observation of Hydroxyapatite sample implanted on rabbit subcutaneous neck	Amraoui Zineb and Belamri Djamel	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 5529
The effect of contaminating neutrons appears with the 18MV photon beam	Mustapha Assalmi and El Yamani Diaf	Morocco, Morocco	Submission 5895
The Importance of Trans-European Road Network Standards and Highway Tunnel Operation Regulation in Tunnel Operation Performance	Burak Koçhan, Emine Çoruh and Metin Mutlu Aydın	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 6382
POMEGRANATE PEEL EXTRACT AS GREEN CORROSION INHIBITOR FOR COPPER IN 1M HCl SOLUTION	Hayat Marmi, Chahinez Siad, Saida Marmi, Abdelouahad Chala and Souhila Marmi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 6635
Effect of solvent concentration and the varieties of solvent on the recovery of phenolic compounds of orange peel	Sihem Haya and Rachida Rihani	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 6655
Assessment of energy potential from the Municipal Solid Waste Landfills in Oran (Western Algeria)	Ahmed Addou, Islam Safia Abdelli, Sanaa Dahmane and Fatiha Abdelmalek	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7230
Conservation of bacteria by encapsulation in PEG and silica gel.	Manel Sebouai, Ali Aksas and Widad Sobhi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7247

Session 2.7		21 JULY 2022 11:00-12:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Numerical study of ZnO/CdS/CdSnP2 solar cells	Moufdi Hadjab, Olga Guskova, Hamza Bennacer and Mohamed Issam Ziane	Algeria, Algeria, Germany, Algeria	Submission 7287
Azo dye degradation by adsorption process using experimental design	Amel Belayachi, Benderdouche Nouredine, Hanane Belayachi, Sarra Bourahla, Benaouda Bestani and Cherif Haddad	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7622
Akıllı Sensörlerin Gelişimi ve Akıllı Şebekeler İçin Fiber Optik Titreşim Sensörlerinin İncelenmesi	Mehmet Güçyetmez and Şekip Esat Hayber	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 7916
Numerical Investigation of Capacitively Coupled Water Vapor Plasma for Species Production	Ziane Kechidi, Abdelatif Tahraoui, Nouredine N. Rebiai and Ahmed Redha Benrekia	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 8432
Analysis and Experiment of Interaction between the Spherical Mobile Robot and Soft Terrain	Minggang Li, Hanxu Sun	China	Submission 9210
Choosing Adequate Centrifugal Pump	Abed Mourad, Ali Bedjaoui and Telli Abdelmoutia	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 9249
Preconditioned conjugate gradient methods for absolute value equations	Nassima Anane and Mohamed Achache	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 9682
Detection of COVID-19 and Viral pneumonia using Transfer Learning.	Fidel Morris Omollo and İsmail Şahin	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1137
Gemi kompresör sisteminin Hata Türü ve Etkileri Analizi (FMEA) yöntemi yardımıyla risk analizi	Haydar Bacioğlu, Bulut Ozan Ceylan and Yasin Arslanoğlu	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 0334
Beton Pompası Elektro-Hidrolik Devre Tasarımı ve Analizi	Ahmet Mercan and Mahmut Can Şenel	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1002

Session 2.8		21 JULY 2022 11:00-12:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Ağır Hizmet Taşıtları için Elektromekanik Disk Fren Sistemi Modellemesi, Simülasyonu ve Deneysel Doğrulaması	İbrahim Can Güteryüz and Özgün Başer	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 0794
Frictionless contact problem in piezoelectricity	Siham Smata and Nemira Lebri	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 6118
Machining of Al2024-SiC Metal Matrix Nanocomposites with CNC Method	Abdullah Hasan Karabacak and Aykut Çanakçı	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 0101
CNC Machining of B4C Reinforcement Metal Matrix Nanocomposites	Abdullah Hasan Karabacak and Müslim Çelebi	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 5110
Exergy Analysis of Stroke to Bore Ratio Effects in Spark Ignition Engines	İsmet Sezer	Turkey	Submission 9351
Fractional Order Small Signal Based P-TID Controller Design for an Induction Motor	Haris Calgan	Turkey	Submission 7619
Measuring and Control Circuit Design and Implementation for Sensorless Control of Induction Motor	Erdem Ilten	Turkey	Submission 7800
Veri Gizleme için Derin Öğrenme Yöntemlerinin Kullanımı	Mehmet Zeki Konyar	Turkey	Submission 8246
Some Improvement Inequalities Involving Integral	Hamdullah Başaran and Mehmet Gürdal	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1842
Heating performances study of heat pump system using the traditional working fluid HFC-R134a and its potential substitutes (HFO-R1234yf and HFO-R1234ze(E)): Energetic analysis and comparison	Youcef Maalem, Abdnour Zerfa and Hakim Madani	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2698

Session 2.9		21 JULY 2022 11:00-12:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Phase Behavior and Testing of R13I1/R152a Mixed Refrigerant System in Heating Machinery	Youcef Maalem, Mohammed Mehemmai and Hakim Madani	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 4395
An Improved Lightweight multi-stream CNN-SVM for Dynamic Hand Gesture Recognition based UWB radar	Djazila Souhila Korti and Zohra Slimane	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 8191
Detecting Defects Using Non Destructive Magnetic Flux Leakage Testing	Kamel Belkhiri, Abdelhak Abdou and Tarik Bouchala	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1581
Soil-pile interaction effects on seismic fragility of single concrete pier	Foudhil Lemsara, Tayeb Bouzid and Djarir Yahiaoui	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 0251
Emet Borik Asit Atığının Seramik Malzeme Üretiminde Kullanılabilirliğinin Araştırılması	Çetin ÖZTÜRK, Atilla EVCİN, Zeynep AYGÜZER	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 6700
Preparation, characterization and photocatalytic application of nano cobalt ferrite in AG 25 treatment	Fatima Zohra Benkrifa, Chaimaa Hachemi, Ali Belhaine, Fatiha Abdelmalek and Ahmed Addou	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 4649
Optimizing the Wind Power Generation Cost in the Tirumala Region of India	Prasun Bhattacharjee, Rabin K. Jana and Somenath Bhattacharya	India, India, India	Submission 4825
Mathematical modeling and simulation of the piezoelectric accelerometer	Lina Aissaoui, Zine Ghemari, Mabrouk Defdaf and Mohamed Razi Morakchi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 4385
Heterogeneous photocatalytic degradation of AG25 by peroxydisulfate actived by MgFe2O4 nano composites under UV light irradiation	Chaimaa Hachemi, Fatima Zohra Benkrifa, Ali Belhaine, Ahmed Addou and Fatiha Abdelmalek	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 6965
Production And Microstructure Investigations of 316L Stainless Steel Reinforced Copper Matrix Composites	Sedat Alperen Tunc, Aykut Canakci and Abdullah Hasan Karabacak	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 4204

Session 2.10		21 JULY 2022 12:00-13:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Investigation of Mechanical Properties of Cu-316L Metal-Metal Composites Produced by Powder Metallurgy Method	Sedat Alperen Tunc, Aykut Canakci and Abdullah Hasan Karabacak	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 8371
Part I. A probabilistic soft set approach to decision making problems	Arzu Erdem Coşkun	Turkey	Submission 2643
Part 2. A probabilistic soft multiset approach to group decision making problems	Arzu Erdem Coşkun	Turkey	Submission 3118
Studies of Photo-catalytic degradation of Basic Red dye under solar irradiation	Amel Hamadi, Hiba Kais and Nacera Yeddou-Mezennere	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 6976
Kahramanmaraş Yöresindeki Karaçamın (Pinus nigra Arnold.) Bonitet Sınıfı ile Bazı Toprak Özellikleri Arasındaki İlişkiler	Emre Kuzugüdenli and Hüseyin Göktaş	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 7405
Agregat Stabilitesinin Bazı Toprak Değişkenleriyle Modellenmesi	Emre Kuzugüdenli and Hüseyin Göktaş	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 7919
MEMS accelerometer and gyroscope in navigation technology	Razi Morakchi, Zine Ghemari, Defdaf Mabrouk, Abderrahmane Guezi, Selman Djeffal and Merwane Khebal	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 8556
Zaman Domeninde Sonlu Farklar Yöntemi ile İki Boyutlu Elektromanyetik Dalga Yayılımı Simülasyonu	Sunay Güler	Turkey	Submission 1186
DFT investigations of the half-metallic double perovskite oxide Ba ₂ CeCoO ₆	Hadjer Bendjilali, Abbas Chahed, Habib Rozale and Abdelkader Bouhenna	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2772
SOME RESULTS ON PAULI GROUP	Esra Kırmızı Çetinalp	Turkey	Submission 7391

Session 2.11		21 JULY 2022 12:00-13:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
On a Multipoint Fractional Boundary Value Problem in a Fractional Sobolev Space	Chahra Kechar and Abdelouaheb Ardjouni	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 8944
IMPLEMENTATION OF DCS SYSTEM FOR COMPRESSED AIR PRODUCTION UNIT	Sihem Kechida and Ayab Ahmed	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1510
An adsorption parametric study for removal of antibiotic drug by activated carbon derived from cacao shells	Hiba Kais, Amel Hamadi and Nacera Yeddou-Mezenner	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 8894
IoT based platform for fuel tank truck monitoring and management	Hamza Benyezza, Mounir Bouhedda, Sofiane Bendamardji, Reda Kara and Yahia Aniba	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7235
Investigation of structural, microstructural, and optical properties of Mg /ZnO thin films Using spray pyrolysis Techniques	Sabrina Roguai and Abdelkader Djelloul	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7684
The effect of direct current applications on cell size and culture medium conductivity of the microalgae <i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	Osman Kk, İlhami Tzn and Yařar Aluř	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 2584
Methylene blue adsorption from aqueous solutions with activated carbon from olive industry solid waste	Sinem Gneř and Dilek Angin	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 5688
Effect of sintering temperature on mullite-cordierite ceramics.	Alima Mebrek, Hadda Rezzag, Sabrina Ladjama, Sabri Bouchoucha and Azzedine Grid	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2187
Generating α -dense curves in non-convex sets to solve a Hlder global optimization	Djaouida Guettal and Mohamed Rahal	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 8110
Non Destructive Testing by Magnetic Leakage Flux Applied to Ferromagnetic Parts	Merwane Khebal, Abdelhak Abdou, Tarik Bouchala, Mohamed Razi Morakchi and Abderrahmane Aboura	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7599

Session 2.12		21 JULY 2022 12:00-13:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
study of the properties of a thermoelectric material	Bouhenna Abdelkader, Benyahia Karima, Boualem Kada and Bendjilali Hadjer	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 5577
First-principles calculation of electronic and mechanical properties of Half-Heusler HfNiSn	Wassila Abir Drouni	Algeria	Submission 1713
Study the behavior of silica intended for the production of silicon for photovoltaic application by numerical simulation	Aissa Kefaiifi and Abdelkrim Kheloufi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 9842
Ab-initio investigations of physical proprieties of the Ba-based perovskite oxide.	Chebbab Insaf, Chiker Fafa, Khachai Houari and Ezzine Kawther Fatima Zohra	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 4960
Analysis and Study of the Reinforcement of Unstable Embankments by Geosynthetics	Messaouda Boutahir Born Bencheikh, Assia Aidoud, Fatima Zohra Benamara, Nacera Khaldi, Meriem Dorbani and Lazhar Belabed	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7720
Katı Yakıtlı Model Roket Tasarımı ve Uçuş Simülasyonu	Furkan Çetin, Berk Demirkan, Abdilbaki Kıvrak and Tarık Ünler	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 9759
Measuring the concentration of some heavy metals and their adverse effects in the soil adjacent to the Gharraf River, Shatrah Branch: Pathological study	Mohammed A. Hasan1, Ibtihaj A. Kadhim	Iraq, Iraq	mail submission 1
Effect of DNN Approximation for Channel Estimation and Signal Detection on OFDM Applications	Bircan Çalışır	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 9284
Atomic force microscopy as powerful technique to unravel the building block morphology of amyloidogenic proteins at the nanoscale level	Carlos Marcuello	spain	Submission 5164
Global Solar Radiation Estimation Using The Smoothing Spline Algorithm	Ayse Gül Kaplan and Yusuf Alper Kaplan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 2964

Session 2.13		21 JULY 2022 13:00-14:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Caching on 802.15.4 IoT Named Data Networks	Sedat Bilgili, Gokce Manap and Alper Demir	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 3517
Investigation of structural, microstructural, and optical properties SnO2 thin films by spray pyrolysis	Roguai Sabrina, Djelloul Abdelkader	Algeria, Algeria	mail submission 2
kNN method in functional nonparametric regression	Somia Guenani and Bouabsa Wahiba	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 4519
A Numerical Study for Heat Sink Design of Ferrofluid based Passive Cooling System	Jaswinder Singh Mehta, Rajesh Kumar, Harmesh Kumar and Harry Garg	India, India, India, India	Submission 1589
In-vitro Synergic antioxidant activity between aqueous extract and methanolic extract of Teucrium polium Using Electrochemical Method (Cyclic Voltammetry)	El Kolli Hayet, El Kolli Meriem and Boussoualim Naouel	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 5515
IMPROVEMENT OF NETWORK LIFETIME IN WBAN USING RESIDUAL ENERGY.	Matthew Iyobhebhe	Nigeria	Submission 7438
High Resolution Imaging of the Eastern Algeria Segment Slab Trace using Dispersion Curves Derived from Two-Stations Technique	Selma Lamiri, Zohir Radi and Khalissa Layadi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 6763
Design and optimize in stand-alone of photovoltaic fuel pumping systems	DJERIOU SALIM, BELHADJ Abdelkader and ANWER HIMER	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	mail submission 23
Estimation of binary parameters interaction coefficients for binary mixture VLE Data using EXCEL-Comparison with ChemSep Application	Bouchemella Houria and Salou Khadija	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 5444
Airline Passenger Number Estimation with Regression Analysis Based Genetic Algorithm	Ukbe Üsame Uçar	Turkey	Submission 7105

Session 2.14		21 JULY 2022 14:00-15:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Analysis of Factors Affecting Raw Milk Yield with SWARA Method	Ukbe Ucar	Turkey	Submission 4417
DETECTING HIGH-RISK AREAS FOR LUMPY SKIN DISEASE IN CATTLE USING DEEP LEARNING FEATURES	Musa Genemo	Turkey	Submission 4503
Investigation of Structural, microstructural and optical properties of zinc oxide and Fe-doped ZnO nanoparticles prepared by simple coprecipitation method	Roguai Sabrina, Djelloul Abdelkader	Algeria, Algeria	mail submission 3
Upper Mantle beneath Tunisian from Shear-Wave Splitting	Zohir Radi, Khalissa Layadi and Selma Lamiri	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 4683
Grid Search Parameter Tuned Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average Model to Forecast Wind Power Generation	Akın Özçift	Turkey	Submission 2827
Study on the Effect of Adding Diatomite in the Form of Gravel 4/6 in Mortar to Improve the Thermal Insulation of Buildings.	Housseem Hachemi and Djahida Mahmoudi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1036
Assessment of a topical emulsion containing a local herbal extract	Fouzia Benoudjit, Jihad Cherifi, Fatma Zohra Benyoucef and Imene Hamoudi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 4084
Essential oils composition of two local aromatic herbs	Fouzia Benoudjit, Dabbia Mansouri and Nawel Djabali	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 4894
Toward to develop a Personal Family Social Network	Kahoul Maroua and Telli Abdelmoutia	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1661
Toward to develop a Specific Academic Social Network Application	Fatima Zahra Aoubid and Telli Abdelmoutia	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1906

Session 2.15		21 JULY 2022 14:00-15:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
APPLICATION OF DECISION TREE AND EXTREME LEARNING MACHINE FOR BEARING VIBRATION BASED CONDITION MONITORING	Riadh Euldji, Mouloud Boumahdi and Mourad Bachene	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 6278
Deneysel Elde Edilen Grafen Oksit Sentezlerinin SEM ve TEM Analizleri	Ömer Laçın	Turkey	Submission 0500
Hücreyel Genetik Algoritma ile İnsansız Hava Araçlarında Yol Planlama	Ahmet Gezer, Önder Turan and Tolga Baklacioğlu	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 5368
İnsansız Hava Aracı Performans Modeline Dayalı Yol Planlama	Ahmet Gezer, Önder Turan and Tolga Baklacioğlu	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 8459
Analysis of the heat given to the outside by the built-in oven boilers according to different material types by finite element method	Hakan Emin Erciyes, Selcan Gürmen, Fatih Semiz, Hakan Kazan	Turkey	Submission 2540
Estimate the position of mobility edge for Bose-Einstein condensate in 3D disordered potentials by using the Drude conductivity	Hanane Benmahdoub, Afifa Yedjour, Mohammed Benmahdjoub and Kenza Boutami	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1424
Effect of Agave Fiber Content on Properties of Poly(3-Hydroxybutyrate-Co-3-Hydroxyhexanoate) Biocomposites	Mustapha Kaci, Celia Idres, Nadjet Dehouche, Carole Lainé and Stéphane Bruzard	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, France, France	Submission 6338
Mechanical response of functionally graded beams with porosities	Abdelkader Safa, Lazreg Hadji and Mohamed Bouraada	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 4510
The Magnetic and Curie Temperature Investigations of Co ₂ NbGa Full Heusler Alloy with EFT Method	Semih Doğruer, Evren Görkem Özdemir and Ziya Merdan	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 4846
Improving the Thermal Protection Performance of a Representative Battery Cell by using Different Fin Arrangements	Ferhat Kilinc, Ahmet Can Çapar and Ümit Nazlı Temel	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 9308

Session 2.16		21 JULY 2022 14:00-15:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
in vitro anti inflammatory and hemolytic activities of qaeous extract from scabiosa succisa roots	Hadjer Sekhri Zeggar and Nouredine Charef	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 3189
Crustal thickness of Guelma basin in North East Algeria from P Receiver Function analysis using short period data	Salim Guettouche and Mahfoud Djeddar	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1925
Ayçiçeğinde Farklı Sıra Aralıklarının Verim Ve Verim Unsularına Etkisi	Merve Nur İnce Yıldız	Turkey	Submission 6074
Design structure Matrix coupled with Genetic Algorithm for Enhancing Manufacturing Process: A Study Case on Grader's Blade Bull	Larbi Bendada, Mourad Brioua, Selman Djeffal and Mohamed Razi Morakchi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1504
Different MEMS-based accelerometers types	Mohamed Razi Morakchi, Zine Ghemari, Mabrouk Defdaf, Merwane Khebal, Selman Djeffal and Lina Aissaoui	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7758
Bilgisayar Destekli Dizin Programları ve TürkSözDiz Yazılımı	Mehmet Bozuyula	Turkey	Submission 1940
Mechanical Behavior of Thin CrN Layers, Deposited by DC Magnetron Sputtering on 41Cr4 Type Steels	Bouaicha Salah, Mohamed Zine Touhami, Riad Badji, K. Laggoune	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	mail submission 4
Semi-functional partial linear regression	Kedir Nassima Houda, Benchikh Tawfik and Nacéri Amina	Algeria	Submission 3407
Tıbbi ve Aromatik Bitki Olarak Tarhun (Artemisia dracuncululus L.)' Bitkisinin Değerlendirilmesi	Ayşe Kara and Emre Çağlak	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 2018
Optimization study of perovskite-based solar cells using R-soft package	Maroua Chahmi, Mounir Bouras, And Moufdi Hadjab	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	mail submission 5

Session 2.17		21 JULY 2022 15:00-16:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Improvement of Shortbread Nutritional Quality with Sprouted Chickpea Flour	Keremet Mirbek Kyzy and Aichurok Mazhitova	Kyrgyzstan, Kyrgyzstan	Submission 2358
İNCONEL 718 MALZEMESİNİN İŞLENEBİLİRLİĞİ ÜZERİNE İNCELEME	Alican Kılıç and Mehmet Alper Sofuoğlu	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 9315
Formulating Dune Sand Concrete as a Replacing Material for Ordinary Concrete	Mohamed Ladjel, Mohamed Chemrouk and Abdessamed Azzez Rahmani	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 4155
Use of a new ecological inhibitor for corrosion of pipelines steels in an acid environment	Slimane Kherief, Hamza Bentrach, Mounir Djellab, Bouzid Bouamra, Hicham Taoui and Abdelouahad Chala	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 0732
DEVELOPMENT OF HYBRID ENERGY HARVESTING SYSTEM FOR LOW POWER DEVICES IN IoT APPLICATION	Ojingwa Onyinye, Mohammed A.S, Usman A.U and Kolo J.G	Nideria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria	Submission 0526
Improvement of the performance of the photovoltaic power plant of the Oued El Kebrit situated in Souk ahars city	Samira Boumous, Zouhir Boumous, Samia Latrèche and Hamou Nouri	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 8875
Comparative study of the efficiency of a photovoltaic power plant connected to the electricity grid	Samira Boumous, Zouhir Boumous, Fatima Zohra Kebbab, Sabah Louarem and Hamou Nouri	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 9737
Synthesis of Lead Sulfide for Supercapacitor Application	Satiye Korkmaz	Turkey	Submission 5203
Application of an Artificial Neural Network for Modeling the Quantities of Construction and Demolition Wastes in Four Egyptian Governorates	Nehal Elshaboury and Tarek Attia	Egypt, Egypt	Submission 1701
Fractional Order PI Controller for Wireless Power Transfer with High Efficiency	Farhan Ahmad and Metin Demirtaş	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 4309

Session 2.18		21 JULY 2022 15:00-16:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Growth of p-adic entire solution of some fonctionnelle equations	Salih Bouternikh and Tahar Zerzaihi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 3242
Photothermal Investigation of Magnesium Oxysulfate Cement	Rim Zgueb and Nouredine Yacoubi	Tunisia, Tunisia	Submission 9907
Towards Perfect Monitoring of Water Supply System	Kouloughli Chemseddine and Telli Abdelmoutia	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 4046
Akar Görüntülerden Makine Öğrenmesine Dayalı Kimlik Tespiti	Abdullah Kenan Öztürk and Erdem Erkan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 0516
Existence of distributional solutions for nonlinear fractional Schrödinger-poisson system involving new operator	Boutebba Hamza, Lekhal Hakim and Slimani kamel	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	mail submission 6
Mathematical model of jet pump workflow distribution	Denys Panevnyk	Ukraine	Submission 1056
Preparation of isocyanate containing sulfobetaine based reactive hydrogels on solid substrates as enzyme immobilization matrix	Merve Bat Özmatara, Tuğçe Nihal Gevrek Civan and Aişe Ünlü	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 2820
THE MIRROR DESCENT METHOD	Bochra Zeghad	Algeria	Submission 9474
Phytochemical study and iron chelating activity of methanolic extract from scabiosa	Hadjer Sekhri Zeggar and Nouredine Charef	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 0338
EFFECT OF PANEL DIRECTION ON ENERGY GENERATION IN 100kWp SOLAR POWER PLANT	Mehmet Fatih Beyoğlu and Metin Demirtaş	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 0235

Session 2.19		21 JULY 2022 15:00-16:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Gender Classification based on Voice via Transfer Learning	Hüseyin Ezirmik and Fatih Aydın	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 2915
Global existence for reaction-diffusion parabolic system using in image processing	Hana Matallah	Algeria	Submission 4767
Numerical analysis of functionally graded rotating Nano shaft using differential quadrature finite elements method	Ahmed Saimi, Ismail Bensaid and Abdelhamid Hadjoui	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 6158
Simulation of Bluetooth Smart Attendance System with SMS Alert	Auwal Rabiou Dan Sharif, Mariya Garba Mustapha, Abdu Isah, Abdulkadir Habibu Kofar Naisa, Nuhu. A Muhammad and Muhammad Baballe Ahmad	Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria	Submission 4475
Five-Phase Synchronous Machine Design Using Numerical MAXWELL Software	Said Benkaihou, Lakhdar Mazouz, Toufik Tayeb Naas, Rabia Behloul and Elmamoune Halassa	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 0454
Comparisons of Half-Metallic Band Gaps of Li ₂ TiMnO ₆ Double Perovskite via GGA and GGA+mBJ	Evren Görkem Özdemir	Turkey	Submission 9055
Determination of Plant Characteristics of Popcorn Landraces in Turkey	Gülay Zulkadir and Leyla İdikut	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 6352
Effects of combustor parameters on mini turbojet performance under real conditions	Hakan Aygun and Mohammed Rauf Sheikhi	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 5227
Relationship between density and thermal properties of Compressed Earth Block (CEB) based on date palm waste aggregates	Elhoussine Atiki, Bachir Taallah, Kamal Saleh Almeasar, Daifallah Khoudja and Abdelhamid Guettala	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 8236
Effect of date palm ash on shrinkage of earth mortar	Kamal Saleh Almeasar, Bachir Taallah, Elhoussine Atiki, Daifallah Khoudja, Ouarda Izemmouren and Abdelhamid Guettala	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 6714

Session 2.20		21 JULY 2022 16:00-17:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Multi objective Optimization of activities networks in concurrent engineering	Larbi Bendada, Mourad Brioua, Selman Djeffal and Mohamed Razi Morakchi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7737
Adsorption of pharmaceutical pollutant on Algerian clay	Kheira Addouch, Soumia Seddari, Hakima Cherifi, Radia Yous and Razika Khaladi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2562
Performance Assessment of the Quality of Service of a GSM Network in Jigawa State Nigeria	Agburu Ahinoy'Ohe Ogah Adikpe	Nigeria	Submission 2623
Estimation of carbon footprint in highways: A preliminary study in Aksaray	Samed Aksoy and Ebru Koçak	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1383
Temporal Characteristics of Air Pollutants (PM10, SO2, NOx, NO2, O3, and CO) and health risk assessment: Preliminary case study in Aksaray, Turkey	Sibel Albayrak and Ebru Koçak	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 0837
Olivin Kumu Kullanılarak Yüksek Sıcaklık Direnci Arttırılmış Geleneksel ve Alkali Aktive Edilmiş Cürüflü Harçlar	Murat Öztürk	Turkey	Submission 8787
Sentetik Endüstriyel Verilerde Tahmine Dayalı Analitik için Makine Öğrenimi Yöntemleri	Meltem Supurtulu	Turkey	Submission 3523
Endoskopik Görüntülerden Gastrointestinal Hastalıkların Derin Öğrenme Tabanlı Yaklaşım ile Tespiti	Fatih Demir	Turkey	Submission 9751
Natural convection cooling of LEU Target Plates for Molybdenum-99 Production.	Missaoui Sayah, Salhi M'Hamed, Mohammedi Brahim and Mellal Nacim	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7087
Contribution to improving the performance of HV electrical transmission cables	Faouzi Hassaine, Nacereddine Guettaf, Houria Salhi, Fatima Zohra Cherrad, Chakib Drif and Hamou Nouri	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2169

Session 2.21		21 JULY 2022 16:00-17:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Impact of wind force on the vibration of the bearings in the aerogenerator system	Fatima Zohra Cherrad, Sabah Louarem, Fatima Zohra Kebbab, Chabane Djabali, Samira Boumous and Hamou Nouri	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 9862
Akciğer Kanseri Histopatolojik Görüntülerinin EfficientNet Kullanılarak Sınıflandırılması	Abdulkadir Albayrak	Turkey	Submission 9203
The Effect of A New Generation Antioxidant Combination on Matrix Metalloproteinases in Diabetic Wound Healing	Elif Naz Alver, Kanuni Barbaros Balabanlı, Fatma Nur Tuğcu Demiröz and Şule Coşkun Cevher	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 7954
Training of Multilayer Perceptrons using Salp Swarm Optimization Algorithm	Durmuş Furkan Atli and Şaban GÜlcÜ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 2435
Four approaches of Jacobi elliptic functions to solving the time-fractional (2+1)-dimensional dispersive long-wave system	Medjahed Djilali	Algeria	Submission 2552
Existence and uniqueness results of self-similar solutions of the space-fractional diffusion equation	Nora Ouagueni and Yacine Arioua	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 4873
Stability of a plane Poiseuille flow of non-Newtonian Fluid across a corrugated channel.	Mohamed Madi, Abdessamade Rafiki and Khalid Souhar	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 5109
Experimental Investigation of the Effect of Cone Tip Diameter on the Preheater Cyclone Separator Efficiency	Yalçın Yeşil	Turkey	Submission 9561
Investigation of Ear Features of Landraces Popcorn Populations Growing in Turkey	Gülay Zülkadir and Leyla İdikut	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 3925
An association analysis between the T309G polymorphism of the MDM2 gene and the occurrence of Bladder Cancer.	Zohra Touala-Chaila, Rym-Khadidja Abderrahmane, Nihad Hessani, Hind Drider, Imene Derbouz and Djebaria Naima Meroufel	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7675

Session 2.22		21 JULY 2022 16:00-17:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Markov Model Applied to the Earthquake Magnitude in the Aegean Region of Turkey	Gamze Özel, Ceren Ünal and Tuba Eroglu Azak	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 4793
Analitik Hiyerarşi Süreci Kullanılarak Oyun Bilgisayarı Seçimi	M. Hanefi Calp and Resul Bütüner	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 2305
Grey Incidence Analysis for Covid19 New Cases and Deaths in Selected European Countries According to Türkiye	Erdal Aydemir and Tunahan Turhan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 6649
Characterization of the Earthquakes in the Aegean Region of Turkey via Shannon Entropy	Gamze Özel, Hatice Nur Karakavak and Senem Tekin	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 9321
Şifreleme Algoritmaları Kullanılarak Bir Mesajlaşma Uygulamasının Geliştirilmesi	M. Hanefi Calp and Resul Bütüner	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 9406
Makine Öğrenmesi Algoritmaları ile EEG Sinyallerinden Duygu Tanıma	Resul Bütüner and M. Hanefi Calp	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 5387
Yapay Sinir Ağları Kullanılarak Parkinson Hastalığının Teşhis Edilmesi	Resul Bütüner and M. Hanefi Calp	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 8439
Some embeddings between variable Besov-type spaces	Zouheyr Zeghad	Algeria	Submission 3890
Feature selection in the context of creating a hybrid classification model for the diagnosis of heart disease	Mahmut Dirik	Turkey	Submission 5627
Osmaniye’de Satılan Bazı Makarnaların Temel Özellikleri ve Türk Gıda Kodeksi Makarna Tebliğine Uygunlukları	Halef Dizlek	Turkey	Submission 1649

Session 2.23		21 JULY 2022 17:00-18:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Inverter Design and Implementation for An Off-Grid Wind Energy System	Ahmet Toprak and Ramazan Akkaya	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 3984
Study of the microstructure and tribological behaviour of boron-enhanced ductile cast iron by the powder-pack boriding method.	Djihad Charmati and Mohamed Zine Touhami	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 3647
Import and Export Data Behavior Analysis for OECD20 Countries in Covid19 Process using Grey Incidence Method	Erdal Aydemir and Cengiz Gazeloğlu	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 4839
Use of microscopic techniques for detection of sarcocystis.spp in meat products	Saliha Lakehal, Ammar Ayachi and Omar Bennoune	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 5329
Comparative analysis of VISSIM with other traffic simulation techniques	Muhammad Usama and Muhammad Usman Farooqi	Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 3800
VISSIM simulation for reducing traffic congestion problem: A case study	Aman Ullah, Muhammad Usama and Muhammad Usman Farooqi	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 4628
Uçucu Kül Esaslı Geopolimer ile Sulu Çözeltilerden Metil Violet Giderimi	Büşra Aydın and Evren Ariöz	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 9484
Classification of Plant Diseases with Artificial Intelligence	Elif Akarsu, Burcu Tiryaklı and İbrahim Yücel Özbek	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 7433
Effect of two-directionally porosity distribution on buckling behavior of functionally graded porous beam	Ismail Bensaid, Ahmed Saimi and Ihab Eddine Houalef	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 3451
Accident Detection and Alerting Systems: A Study	Abdulkadir Shehu Bari, Muhammad Abubakar Falalu, Muhammad Auwal Umar, Yakubu Yunusa Sulaiman, Abdullahi Mansur Gamble and Muhammad Baballe Ahmad	Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria	Submission 6953

Session 2.24		21 JULY 2022 17:00-18:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Modeling the wind speed data using a new probability distribution	Lazhar Benkhelifa	Algeria	Submission 4517
Inertia Weight Strategies for Butterfly Optimization Algorithm	Semchedine Moussa and Chabane Boumendjel	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7721
A New Locality Record of <i>Hebeloma mesophaeum</i> (Agaricales: Basidiomycota) in Turkey	Oğuzhan Kaygusuz	Turkey	Submission 9143
<i>Laccaria laccata</i> : A New Locality Record from Western Turkey	Oğuzhan Kaygusuz	Turkey	Submission 6297
Electrochemical studies of bimetallic TiO ₂ alloys as flexible photoanode for dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSC)	Lallali Hayet, Belhousse Samia, Tighilt Fatma-Zohra, Hamdani Khaled, Lasmi Kahina, Bentouami Abdelhadi and Sam Sabrina	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7301
Phytochemical analysis, antioxidant and antibacterial activities in vitro of polar extracts of <i>Moltkia ciliata</i>	SoumaiaChihi, Oumelkheir RAHIM	Algeria, Algeria	mail submission 7
Biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles and determination of antibacterial activity – A Review	SoumaiaChihi, Oumelkheir RAHIM	Algeria, Algeria	mail submission 8
Synthesis of ZnAl ₂ O ₄ /MoS ₂ nanocomposite for the degradation of Basic Blue 41 dye under visible light	Youssef Fahoul, Karim Tanji and Abdelali El Gaidoumi	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 9012
Effect study different weave orientations on the mechanical properties of the polymer matrix using jute and marble powder	Khaldoune Abd Raouf	Algeria	Submission 8633
The effect of compost addition on the ecological restoration of forest soils degraded by grazing	Ayoub Allam, Mohamed Zouidi, Abdelkrim Kefifa and Amine Habib Borsali	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 4630

Session 2.25		21 JULY 2022 17:00-18:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Business and Government-financed GERD Analysis for Türkiye and Far-East Countries Using Grey Theory	Tunahan Turhan and Cengiz Gazeloğlu	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 2437
Study of the test for periodicity in the exponential autoregressive model	Asma Yousfi and Ahlem Ghourar	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 3194
Referans İdeal Metot (RIM) Kullanılarak Alüminyum Otomobil Panel Malzemelerinin Seçimi	Batuhan Özakin	Turkey	Submission 2797
Shock filters and Self-similar solutions for contour enhancement in image processing	Achour Hossemddine	Algeria	Submission 9045
ZnO-Zn ₂ TiO ₄ mixed metal oxides derived from LDHs nanostructured for caffeine photocatalytic degradation: In-situ ultrasound-induced polyol-medium desig	Fatima Zahra Janani, Alaâeddine Elhalil and Noureddine Barka	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 9663
Antifungal activity of Lactobacillus strains isolated from camel milk	Nafissa Sahel, Fadela Chougrani, Abderrahim Cheriguene and Zinab Hamani	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 9610
STUDY ON TIME SCALE THE GLOBAL ASYMPTOTIC STABILITY IN NONLINEAR NEUTRAL INTEGRO-DYNAMIC EQUATIONS	Ibtissem Daira	Algeria	Submission 5784
Salgı Tüyelerinin Matematiksel Karşılaştırılması	Ali Özdemir and Canan Özdemir	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 5028
Fault detection of PV systems using convolutional neural networks and thermal imaging	Hale Bakır	Turkey	Submission 7045
The Impact of the Energy Management and Monitoring System: A Review	Aliyu Hassan Muhammad, Ibrahim Umar Tofa, Abdu Isah, Abubakar Sani Muhammad, Adamu Bello, Auwal Salisu Yunusa and Muhammad Baballe Ahmad	Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria	Submission 6468

Session 2.26		21 JULY 2022 18:00-19:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Performance Evaluation of a Parabolic Trough Power Plant Under the Climatic Conditions of the City of M'Sila, Algeria	Khaled Bouchareb, Nabila Ihaddadene and Khellaf Belkhiri	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7504
Techno-Economic Assessment of a 100 MW Solar Tower Power Plant in the Algerian Climate: A Case Study of M'Sila	Khaled Bouchareb, Khellaf Belkhiri, Nabila Ihaddadene and Khaoula Ikhlef	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 0223
Synthesis of Magnetic Biochar Based Beads: Application as Magnetically Separable Adsorbent for Aqueous Cd (II)	Dhirar Ben Salem, Abdelkader Ouakouak, Fouzia Touahra and Julia Martin	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Spain	Submission 3001
Sürdürülebilir Yaklaşım: Deri Dokuma Kilimler	Meruyert Kaygusuz and Güler ÖncÜ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 0348
Investment Optimization of Hybrid Energy Systems in Yemen	Ahmed Mohammed Saleh and Tahir Mahmood	Yemen, Pakistan	Submission 4826
KENTSEL ATIKSUDA ve ATIKSU ARITMA TESİSİNDE PSİKİYATRİ İLAÇLARININ ARAŞTIRILMASI	Fatma Bedük, Senar Aydın, Arzu Ulvi and Mehmet Emin Aydın	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 2420
Sera Üstü Fotovoltaik Sistemin PVsyst Yazılımı Kullanılarak Simülasyonu ve Ekonomik Analizi	Muhammet Raşit Sancar	Turkey	Submission 4820
Zero-sum And Nonzero-sum Differential Games	Rania Benmenni	Algeria	Submission 8543
IoT-Based Data Capture System Using MQTT Protocol	Yehya ANIBA, Mounir BOUHEDDA, Mourad BACHENE, Hamza BENYEZZA, Sakina MOULAI MOSTEFA and Chaimaa LARBI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	mail submission 9
Raylı Sistem Araçlarında Enerji Verimliliğinin İyileştirilmesi	Eren Aksu and Mahmut Kaplan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 8205

Session 2.27		21 JULY 2022 18:00-19:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Stability Analysis of Thermosolutal Convection with Soret and Dufour Effects in a Porous Collector under a Uniform Magnetic Field	Selma Lounis, Redha Rebhi, Nouredine Hadidi and Amina Ould Larbi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 4201
Stability Analysis of Thermosolutal Convection with Dufour and Soret Effects in a Porous Collector under a Uniform Magnetic Field	Selma Lounis, Redha Rebhi, Nouredine Hadidi and Amina Ould Larbi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 6273
GÖRÜNTÜ İŞLEME İLE ÖRME KUMAŞLARDA BONCUKLANMA DEĞERLENDİRMESİ	Kardelen Baltacı, Serap İlayda Çınar, İrem Yolcu, İrem Ülgen, Ercan Şenyiğit and Gökhan Yaşar	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 0728
Systematic investigation of the adsorption and inhibition properties of a new clickable 1,2,3-triazole compound for mild steel in 1 M HCl medium	Meryem Hrimla, Lahoucine Bahsis, My Rachid Laamari, Hafid Anane, Miguel Julve and Salah-Eddine Stiriba	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Spain, Spain	Submission 8108
Synthesis of a new fluorescent sensor based on thiazole and investigation of its optical properties	Fatma Göktekin and Duygu Aydın	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 5045
Beslenme ve Sağlık Açısından Kekik (Thymus) Esansiyel Yağları ve Antioksidan Özellikleri	Suveybe Rana Eskicorapçı and Muhammet Doğan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 3248
Sağlıklı Beslenmede Likopenin Yeri ve Önemi	Hicret Kevser Deveci and Muhammet Doğan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 8156
Micromagnetic simulation for island type magnetic device to understand magnetic change depending on temperature	Ibrahim Cınar	Turkey	Submission 4052
Simulation of defects of the asynchronous machine and the inverter	Zouhir Boumous, Samira Boumous and Mahdi Benaouadj	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 3284
asynchronous machine modeling with speed adjustment	Zouhir Boumous, Samira Boumous and Yacine Djeghader	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 3619

Session 2.28		21 JULY 2022 18:00-19:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Kimyasal Tankerlerde Tank Operasyonlarındaki Yangın Risklerinin FTA Metodu ile İncelenmesi	Nurettin Büyük and Murat Yorulmaz	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 9507
Adsorption of orange II by new silicate materials	Ali Belhaine, Fatiha Abdelmalek, Mouffok Redouane Ghezzer and Ahmed Addou	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7327
Fonksiyonel Besinler ve Fitokimyasallar	Betul Yanar and Muhammet Doğan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 3068
Antioksidanca Zengin Beslenme	Merve Gizem Karaboga and Muhammet Doğan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 7862
INSPECTING THE THERMOELECTRIC RESPONSE AND MECHANICAL STABILITY OF NOVEL QUATERNARY HEUSLER COMPOUNDS NiScYZ (Y =Ti, V AND Z=Al, Ga). A DFT INVESTIGATION	Slimane Gheriballah, Youssouf Benazzouzi, Abbes Chahed and Habibe Rozale	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 0751
Effect of boundary conditions on convective heat transfer between parallel plates in the presence of nanofluids: A review	Amir Torabi, Zahra Taheri and Morteza Bayareh	Iran, Iran, Iran	Submission 9924
Development of an Efficient Heterogeneous Copper-Catalyzed Azide-Alkyne Clickable Cycloaddition Reactions	Noura Aflak, Hicham Ben El Ayouchia, Lahoucine Bahsis, Hafid Anane and Salah-Eddine Stiriba	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Spain	Submission 0743
Free vibration analysis of clamped circular laminated plates with curvilinear fibers	Ahmed Guenanou, Abderahim Houmat, Mohammed Hachemi, Khaldoun Bachari and Redouane Chebout	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2492
Beslenmenin Oksidatif Stres ve Bazı Hastalıklara Karşı Önemi	Büşra Ergel and Muhammet Doğan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 2323
Assessment of the coupling of torsional and soft-first-story effects on the seismic response of RC frame buildings	Mansour Ouazir, Abderrahmane Ouazir, Khatima Ouazir and Amin Ouazir	Algeria, Saudi Arabia, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 0823

Session 3.1		22 JULY 2022 9:00-10:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Mitigation of E2E delay in WBAN using Time Division Multiple Access in dual Sink Node.	Matthew Iyobhebhe, Kennedy Aiguobarueghian, Ishaya Chollom Botson, Chukwudi Ezugwu, Usman Omeiza Ahmed, Fatima Ashafa	Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria	Submission 3972
Determination of critical seismic excitation directions for irregular structures at multiple levels	Mansour Ouazir, Abderrahmane Ouazir, Khatima Ouazir and Amin Ouazir	Algeria, Saudi Arabia, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 8973
Manyetik Rezonans Görüntülerini Kullanarak Derin Öğrenme Tabanlı Beyin Tümörlerinin Sınıflandırılması	Burak Taşcı	Turkey	Submission 8936
Systems Having Fractional Order Time Delay and Controller Design	Münevver Mine Özyetkin	Turkey	Submission 0555
The Benefits of Adopting a Wireless Nurse Call System: A Review	Aliyu Hassan Muhammad, Abdulrahman Yusuf Abdullahi, Aminu Abba, Abdu Isah, Abdulkadir Ahmad Yako and Muhammad Baballe Ahmad	Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria	Submission 5968
The Effect of Hybrid Nano-Fluid On Heat Exchangers	Maissa Bouselsal	Algeria	Submission 8656
Proton transfer mechanism and DFT study of structural, electronic, optical and vibrational properties of the benzoic acid	Slimani Yasmine, Boukaoud Abdelali and Abderrahmane Leila	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 3436
Physicochemical characterization of new natural clay (Application to the elimination of anionic dye)	Mecheri Razika, Atia Salem and Zobeidi Ammar	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2185
Synthesis, Corrosion Inhibiting Efficacy of a Ferrocene Ammonium Salt : Experimental and Theoretical Investigation	RAHIM Oumelkheir , ZIOUANI Abdelkadar, MECHERI Razika and ATIA Salem	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	mails submission 10
Importance of naturally derived-enzyme production and its effects on GMO perception	Murat Ay	Turkey	Submission 9869

Session 3.2		22 JULY 2022 9:00-10:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
The retro design of wind turbine blade (Air) using (FARO) measuring arm	Aimeur Noureddine and Menasri Noureddine	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 6680
Study of the role of the binder used in Si-based electrodes of Li-ion batteries	Isma Bozetine, Abdelhak Cheriet, Chafiaa Yaddadene, Fatima Boudeffar, Faiza Tiour, Amar Manseri, Hocine Cheraga and Aissa Keffous	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 6484
OPTO-STRUCTURAL PROPERTIES OF SI-RICH SINX WITH DIFFERENT THICKNESS – MULTILAYER APPROACH-	Faiza Tiour, Abdelmounaim Chetoui, Brahim Mahmoudi, Kheira Bekhedda, Amar Manseri, Amine Mefoued, Chahinez Nasraoui, Hocine Cheraga and Affaf Brik	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1116
Modeling of Tear Index in Paper Production Using Artificial Neural Networks	Erkan Sami Kokten, Selçuk Cılız and Aysin Süleymanoğlu	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 6605
Biological control against Varroa destructor	Belhadji Amina, Abdelli Imane, Hassani Faiçal, Bekkal Brikci Sohayb and Ghalem Sarra	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2374
Artificial neural networks model of chaotic systems. Application to the Colpitts Circuit	Ines Mahmoud and Ayachi Errachdi	Tunisia, Tunisia	Submission 9541
Çoklu İHA'nın Haberleşmesi ile Düşman Ortamının Matematiksel Modellemesi	Ayhan Gültekin, Samet Diri and Yaşar Becerikli	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 3304
Students' Attendance System Using Bluetooth and GSM Module	Muhammad Baballe Ahmad, Yusuf Idris Muhammad, Aminu Abba, Shazali Abbas Ibrahim, Abdulkadir Ahmad Yako and Abdulkadir Sarki Aliyu	Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria	Submission 4280
Identification of imine derivatives and evaluation in vitro their biological activities	Lilia Adjissi, Nadjib Chafai and Chawki Bensouici	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1265

Performance Analysis of a Single-IRS-aided transmission system	Slimane Benmahmoud and El-Hadi Meftah	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 4376
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Session 3.3		22 JULY 2022 9:00-10:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Numerical study of natural convection in a square cavity filled with a nonNewtonian fluid saturated by a porous layer	Ould Larbi Amina, Rebhi Redha, Laidi Maamar and Lounis Selma	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2716
Control over Amplification in Exciton Polariton Condensate	Sergey Borisenok	Turkey	Submission 5171
Hybrid Fiber Reinforced Cementitious Composites at Elevated Temperature: A Review	Ahmed Ali, Muhammad Saud Khan and Safer Ullah Khattak	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 5321
The relationship between systemic amyloidosis and proinflammatory response in Familial Mediterranean Fever disease	Feyzanur Yıldırımtepe çaldıran and Ercan Cacan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 6276
Biometric Traits in Security Systems: Face VS Fingerprints	Chaima Labiod, Lahcene Ziet and Abdelaziz Mokhnache	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 4132
Organik Mikrokirleticiler ve Arıtım Yöntemlerine Genel Bakış	Onur Sözüdoğru	Turkey	Submission 0126
Çayın [Camellia sinensis (L.) O. Kuntze] Kimyasal Bileşimi ve Potansiyel Sağlık Yararları	Seyma Nur Kılıc and Muhammet Doğan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 8680
Sağlıklı ve Popüler Bir İçecek: Papatya Çayı	Gizem Yurdakul and Muhammet Doğan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 4314
BUILDING EVALUATION METHODS AND THEIR IMPACT ON SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT AND ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION	Mohamed Amine Khadraoui, Soumaya Besbas, Marouane Samir Guedouh, Selma Saraoui and Leila Sriti	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 8527
Seismic fragility estimation of single concrete pier considering soil-pile interaction effects	Foudhil Lemsara, Tayeb Bouzid and Djarir Yahiaoui	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 3117

Session 3.4		22 JULY 2022 10:00-11:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
STUDY OF VISUAL COMFORT IN PATIENT ROOMS (CASE OF THE CITY OF BEJAIA IN ALGERIA)	Soumaya Besbas, Mohamed Amine Khadraoui and Noureddine Zemmouri	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2617
Kinematic Design of a Dual Arm Robot in Cell-Culturing, Sterility Testing and Risky Laboratory Areas	Ardit Oseku and Özgün Başer	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 9554
Analysis of Conjugate Mixed Convection of Newtonian Flow along a Vertical Cylinder With MHD effect	Fatma Zohra Saidoune and Zohra Benharkat	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7271
The Effect Of A Heat Génération On Transient Mixed Convective Heat And Mass Transfer Flow Over A Vertical Cylinder	Fatma Zohra Saidoune and Zohra Benharkat	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 3037
Beklemeli Sedimantasyon Testi ile Beklemeli Gluten İndeks Testinin Süne Hasarına Uğramış Buğday Unlarında Mukayesesi	Halef Dizlek	Turkey	Submission 1021
A Study based upon the Effect Of Coconut Husk Ash, recycled Concrete Aggregate And Pet Fiber Over The Strength Aspects Of Concrete	Suhail Mushtaq Khan and Harvinder Singh	India, India	Submission 2076
City Living Labs for Sustainability and Resilience of Climate Change	Neslihan Beden, Nazire Göksu Soydan Oksal, Sema Ariman, Şule Haliloğlu and Hayatullah Ahmadzai	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 3881
Nane Bitkisinin (Mentha piperita Labiatae ve Mentha spicata Labiatae) Beslenme ve Sağlık Üzerine Genel Faydaları	Almina Yılmaz and Muhammet Doğan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 8131
Estimation of the water needs of market gardening crops by two methods (Penman Monteith by CROPWA T 8.0 and Turkish software) in the wilaya of Biskra during the period (1998-2018)	Mebrek Naima, Demnati Fatma, Hiouani Fatima and Kara Nabila	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7632
STUDY OF A LINEAR PARABOLIC DIRICHLET PROBLEM WITH UNKOWN COFFICIENT	Benguesmia Amal	Algeria	mail submission 25

Session 3.5		22 JULY 2022 10:00-11:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
The effect of Hypericum tomentosum's methanolic extract on neutrophils elastase activity	Amina Lamouri and Hamama Bouriche	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 9764
HYDROGEN PEROXIDE SCAVENGING AND ANTIHEMOLYTIC ACTIVITIES OF METHANOLIC EXTRACT OF HYPERICUM TOMENTOSUM	Amina Lamouri and Abderrahmane Senator	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7341
DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF AN EDUCATIONAL FM TRANSMITTER WITH FPGA USING SDR TECHNIQUES	Ahmed Alghhriumi and Bilgehan Erkal	Libya, Turkey	Submission 6845
The Influence of a Porous Layer on Flow Structure and Heat Transfer in a Square Cavity	Manel Fenni, Saber Hamimid and Messaoud Guellal	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 9041
Part.1: Influence of the Refractive Index on a Sensor Based On Two-Dimensional Photonic Crystals	Mehdi Ghoumazi and Mourad Bella	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 8239
Part.2: Influence of the Radius of the Rods on a Sensor Based On Two-Dimensional Photonic Crystals	Mehdi Ghoumazi and Mourad Bella	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 3585
Thermodynamic Modeling of Liquid-Liquid Equilibrium Data and Estimation of New Binary Interaction Parameters for UNIQUAC Model for the ternary system: water/ N,N-Dimethylacetamide/ solvents	Saliha Benaoune and Abdelkrim Merzougui	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1843
Seismic damage analysis of concrete gravity dams	Zahia Abdelli and Abdelhamid Becheur	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1284
Potentiometric sensor properties of a newly synthesized phenol derivative molecule	Oğuz Özbek, Alper Çetin, Esra Koç and Ömer Işıldak	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 3785
A novel PVC membrane strontium(II)-selective potentiometric sensor	Oğuz Özbek	Turkey	Submission 5492

Session 3.6		22 JULY 2022 10:00-11:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Kentsel Arıcılık Kuralları ve Zorlukları	Fehmi Gürel	Turkey	Submission 7152
Geçmişten günümüze petrol lanetibolluk paradoksu; Petrol kısmet mi? Lanet mi?	Nazan Yalcın Erik	Turkey	Submission 1655
Petrol ve doğal gaz tüketiyor mu? Fosil yakıtların enerji sektöründeki geleceği	Nazan Yalcın Erik	Turkey	Submission 1977
A Finite Difference Method For A Coupled Monodimensionnel Viscous Burgers Equation	Ilhem Mous and Abdelhamid Laouar	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 8037
Enhacement of dynamic characteristic response of FG-CNT reinforced composite beams with temperature-dependent material properties	Houalef Ihab Eddine, Bensaid Ismail and Saimi Ahmed	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 3923
4D BASKIDA KATMANLI ÜRETİM ORTAMI VE MALZEME PERSPEKTİFİ	Buğrahan Erdem and Mehmet Alper Sofuoğlu	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 4264
An Integrated Deep Learning Approach with Attention Mechanism for Traffic Flow Forecasting	Ahmet Kara	Turkey	Submission 9700
Weak controllability of fractional singular degenerate problem	Achab Fatma, Rezzoug Imad	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	mail submission 24
Influence of carbonation on the behavior of precast concretes in dry climates in Algeria	Ben Khadda Ben Ammar	Algeria	Submission 1770
Silajdan Elde Edilen Lactobacillus sp. ve Lb. rhamnosus,' un bazı Enzim Aktivitelerinin İncelenmesi	Tugce Turgut, Kemal Gürler and Halit Yücel	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 9233

Session 3.7		22 JULY 2022 11:00-12:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Thermo-Hydraulic Performance Analysis of an Air Heater with Different Types of Ribs Placed on the Absorber Plate	Ferhat Koca	Turkey	Submission 9717
Shifted Legendre Pseudospectral Method for the Solution of Variable Delay Differential Equations	Soner Aydınlık	Turkey	Submission 2377
Forecasting Air Passenger Traffic Flows using Machine Learning Approaches	Batin Latif Aylak	Turkey	Submission 8011
Vector Valued Spaces of Multiplier σ -Convergence	Mahmut Karakuş	Turkey	Submission 6301
Uçak Motoru Yapısı Eğitimleri için Artırılmış Gerçeklik	Osman Güler	Turkey	Submission 6848
ON A FRICTIONAL CONTACT PROBLEM WITH ADHESION IN PIEZOELECTRICITY	Mohamed Selmani	Algeria	Submission 2124
Most methods and techniques used to diagnose the photovoltaic installation	Bait Fateh, Latreche Samia and Khemliche Mabrouk	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 9475
On The Geometric Approach of Differential Equations	Vahide Bulut	Turkey	Submission 9926
Stochastic Optimization of 3-D Printing Process Parameters for Surface Roughness of Polylactic Acid Material using Regression Analysis	Fatih İlgen, Melih Savran and Levent Aydın	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 5835
Growth order of transcendental meromorphic solution of q-difference equation of Painlevé type	Houda Boughaba and Tahar Zerzaihi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 6866

Session 3.8		22 JULY 2022 11:00-12:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Karamanda YetiŖen Salvia Trleri ve Tıbbi nemleri	Fadime Rabia Kayıccılar and Hasan Maral	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 5979
Antioxidant Activity and Chemical Composition of the Essential Oil of <i>Nepeta cilicica</i> Boiss. ex Benth. from Turkey	Hasan Maral, Fadime Rabia Kayıccılar, mer een, Musa Trkmen and AyŖegl Trk Baydır	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 6006
Study On Surface Roughness when Turning Polymer	Afef Azzi, Alima Mebrek and Amina Grairia	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 5989
In vitro scolocidal activity of Atrilpex halimus extract on <i>Echinococcus granulosus</i> protoscoleces	Meryem Benmarce, Assia Haif and Ouarda Ayadi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7312
ThingSpeak Sunucusunu Kullanarak Sıcaklık ve Nem Bilgisini İzleme	Mehmet Duman and Yunus Emre Cengiz	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 3587
Whale Optimization Algorithm (WOA) Control For Grid Connected Solar PV System Using A Series Multi-Cells Inverter	Mohamed-Rdha Skender, Ahmed Medjber, Noureddine Ould Cherchal, Yehya Aniba, Rafik Euldji and Abdelhalim Tlemceni	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 0760
Sensitivity Analysis of Woven Composite Mechanical Properties Under Ballistic Impact	Uur Doan and Emin Snbulolu	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 8711
Sinyalize KavŖaklarda Faz Planının Etkisinin Simlasyon Tekniđi ile İncelenmesi: Kırıkkale rneđi	Burak ayır and Ersin Korkmaz	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 4728
Comparison of some machine learning methods in prediction of failures for an imbalanced dataset	Gazi Bilal Yıldız	Turkey	Submission 5420
A Two-Dimensional Platform Based On Photonic Crystals for the Detection of the Three Gases, Ne, Ag and ND	Mehdi Ghoumazi and Mourad Bella	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2088

Session 3.8		22 JULY 2022 11:00-12:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Single Nucleotide Polymorphism analysis of APOCII Gene in Patients with Hypertriglyceridemia	Nosheen Aslam, Alina Shahzadi and Muhammad Afzal	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 4697
Güneydoğu Anadolu bölgesinde kullanılan yapay gübrelerdeki doğal radyoaktivite ölçümü ve topraktaki etkisi	Mehmet Açık and Mehmet Koşal	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 4361
Pulse Oximeter Based System Prototype to Monitor Vital Signs of COVID-19 Patients in Quarantine	Mert Turanlı, İlhan İlhan and Emrehan Yavşan	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 5078
Hybrid MPPT control for optimizing PV system performance	Rania Benyoucef, Meriem Benbrahim and Samir Abdelhamid	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1231
Kırmızı Pancar Sapı ve Yapraklarının Yün Halı İpliklerin Doğal Boyanmasında Kullanılabilirliği	Selime Çolak and Meruyert Kaygusuz	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1638
CNN-FL Modeli ile Pnömoni Tespitinin Aktivasyon Fonksiyonlarına Göre Karşılaştırılması	Elif Ebru Çaki and Fatih Bayram	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 2298
READING TURKISH VEHICLE PLATES WITH A MOBILE SENSOR AND ARCHIVING FOR SECURITY PURPOSES	Kemal Erdoğan and Mustafa Argun	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 0326
DEEP LEARNING BASED EMERGENCY DETECTION WITH VIDEO PROCESSING	Kemal Erdoğan and Emrullah Eren Yaniç	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 9108
A parametric study on optimization of ring inserted heat exchanger tube	Toygun Dagdevir	Turkey	Submission 2064
Existence and Attractivity for Caputo-Fabrizio Random Fractional Differential Equations	Bekada Fouzia	Algeria	Submission 7246

Session 3.9		22 JULY 2022 11:00-12:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Synthesis and Evaluation of Vasodilator Activity of New 1,4-Dihyropyridine Derivatives	Stiti Mohamed Zakaria, Habila Tahir and Khelili Smail	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 3468
Balıklar için kaçınılmaz bir risk: İnsektisitler	İkbal Demet Nane and Öznur Diler	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 4821
Design and Implementation of Thermoelectric Cooler	Şeyda Uyanık and Hüseyin Demirel	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1234
Biocompatible PVA/p(HEMA-co-MAPTAC) Hydrogel Synthesis and Characterization for Controlled Drug Release	İrem Simge Göregen and Özgür Özay	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 8555
Elaboration and characterization of thin films Cu Inx Ga(x-1) Te2 for photovoltaic applications	Nesrine Menaceur, Ameer Zegadi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 0246
Identification of an Alternative Maintenance Strategy for Railroad Ties	Serdar Dindar	Turkey	Submission 3812
Modeling of monthly sunshine duration using adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system: A Case Study	Lamia Gheraba and Farida Sefha	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 4223
Structural, electronic and magnetic properties of CuCoCrSi	Fadime Irmak Balmumcu and Ziya Merdan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 7781
The Syntheses and Structural Characterizations of Tetraaminomono-(2-Furanylmethyl)-Spiro(N/N) Cyclotriphosphazanium Salts	Hüseyin Akbaş	Turkey	Submission 5819
Comparative study between fuzzy logic and artificial neural network algorithms to detect faults in a PV system	Younes Lahiouel, Samia Latreche and Mabrouk Khemliche	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 6814

Session 3.10		22 JULY 2022 12:00-13:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Rotating MHD Convective Flow Over a Vertical Moving Plate Through a Porous Medium in the Presence of Chemical Reaction and Hall Effects	Zohra Benharkat and Fatma Zohra Saidoune	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 3685
FMCW Radarlarda farklı hedef yapıları için m-pulse MTI filtrelerin performans değerlendirmesi	B. Murat Coşkun, Hüseyin Doğan	Turkey	mail submission 11
Regional variability of the climatic environment of anthropic origin (in M'sila and its surroundings)	Larkat Karima, Bnyahia Azzedine and Allal Meftah	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1773
EFFECT OF THE ELECTROLESS NI-P COATING ON THE PROPERTIES OF CU PARTICLES	Serhatcan Berk Akçay, Onur Güler and Temel Varol	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 5965
İklim Değişikliğinde Katı Atık Yönetimi	Azime Songül Küçüksayacı and Gülden Gök	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 9642
Effect of Ni-P Coating on The Microstructure of Copper-Based Materials Produced by Hot-Pressing	Serhatcan Berk Akçay, Onur Güler and Temel Varol	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 9408
A strategy for binary skin cancer classification based on ensemble of deep learning models	Safa Gasmi, Akila Djebbar and Hayet Farida Merouani	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 9259
Sürtünme Karıştırma İşleminin Al 1050 Alaşımının Aşınma Özelliklerine Etkisi	Semih Mahmut Aktarer, Yaşar Sert and Tefik Küçükömeroğlu	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 9685
Obtaining Deflection Values of Beams Using Finite Element Programs	Ahmet Kubilay Aksakal and Abdullah Gündoğay	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 9379
Effects of dietary tannic acid on Synaptogyrin-1, Synapsin III, and Syntaxin 4 gene expression in monosodium glutamate-induced rats	Medine Sibel Karagaç and Hamid Ceylan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 8296

Session 3.11		22 JULY 2022 12:00-13:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Spam Mail Filtrelemede NB, DVM ve YSA Algoritmaları	Öznur Öztunç Kaymak	Turkey	Submission 7226
Fenol Süstitüe Yeni 1,2,3-Triazollerin Sentezi ve Kolinesteraz Özelliklerinin İncelenmesi	İrfan Şahin and Ferhan Tümer	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 2096
Hydrothermal Deposition of ZnO–CuO Heteronanostructures in the Presence of Surfactant and Investigation of Morphological-Characterizations	Mustafa Biçer	Turkey	Submission 2501
Determination of appropriate quasi-static constitutive equation for the Ti-6Al-4V alloy	Yusuf Furkan Yapan and Mevlüt Türköz	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 9782
Evaluation of Unmanned Marine Vehicles (UMV) Usage Areas using SWOT Analysis	Adnan Abdulvahitoğlu and Aslı Abdulvahitoğlu	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 0642
Risk Analysis of Cement Factory: Temporary Storage Area of Hazardous Waste	Selin Yardimci Dogan, Sezen Coskun and Mehmet Beyhan	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	mail submission 12
MD simulations of the pressure effect on Cerussite mechanical properties	Brahim-Khalil Benazzouz	Algeria	Submission 9309
4-((4-bromofenoksi)metil)-1-(p-tolil)-1H-1,2,3-triazol Bileşiğinin Sentezi ve Anti-Alzheimer Aktivitelerinin Belirlenmesi	Ceren Cuma, Hasan Efendi Yılmaz and Ferhan Tümer	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 5256
Black Cumin Cake inhibitor Effect on aluminum corrosion in 1M HCl	Moussaoui Kamilia, Abderrahmane Sihem and Larkem Hamam	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 5860
A Study On The Dissolution Kinetic of Different Magnesium Forms and Their Effects On pH	Selman Küçükkuvañ, Deniz Tuğçe Algan, Hatice Gül Batur, Şerife Dilek, Aslıhan Küçükçalık, Çağatay Sağır and Emre Fatih Ediz	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 0458

Session 3.12		22 JULY 2022 12:00-13:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Characterization of the Sensitivity in Slab Waveguide Based Optical Sensor under the Temperature Variation	Abdelbaki Cherouana, Idris Bouchama and Abdelhalim Bencheikh	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 8217
Investigation of microstructure and tribological behaviour of boron-reinforced gray cast iron using the powder-pack boring process.	Djihad Charmati and Mohamed Touhami	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1286
Şebeke Destekli GES ile Klor Dozaj Pompalı İçme Suyu Sistemi Tasarımı	Aydın Oğuz Baş and Mehmet Ekici	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 7295
INVESTIGATION OF ANTIVIRAL EFFECT OF SPARTIUM JUNCEUM CRUDE EXTRACTS AGAINST RESPIRATORY SYNCYTIAL VIRUS	Sümeyye Elif Varicioğlu, Rüstem Duman and Hasan Hüseyin Doğan	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 4701
Numerical Solution of Free-Fall Equation Using Two Different Approaches of the Taylor Series Expansion	Mehmet Ekrem Çakmak	Turkey	Submission 8308
Theoretical Investigation of the Structural, Mechanical, Electronic, and Magnetic Properties of new Quaternary Heusler Compound VScRhGe.	Hadjer Frioui, Athmane Meddour and Esmâ Semassel	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7027
Bir Jet Uçak Basınç Duvarı Yapısal Optimizasyonu	Selim Eroğlu and Tunç Apatay	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 7192
Molecular identification of some Fusarium isolates and their chemotypes involved in fusarium head blight on durum wheat in Algeria	Salah Hadjout and Mohamed Zouidi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1400
Optimal Allocation and Tap Position of Voltage Regulator in Distribution Systems	Selçuk Emiroğlu and Talha Enes Gümüş	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 4252
Fetal Health Pattern Classification Using Ensemble Learning	Adem Kuzu and Yunus Santur	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 5349

Session 3.13		22 JULY 2022 13:00-14:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Activity of chemicals in Camellia sinensis extract against prostate cancer	Burak Tüzün	Turkey	Submission 2866
A Comparative Study Of The Analysis Of Engineering Structures By Finite Elements Based On Different Approaches	Maria Legouirah, Meriem Hamadi and Djamal Hamadi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 3341
Boosted Whale Optimization Algorithm	Bahaeddin Türkoğlu	Turkey	Submission 7102
An error estimator and adaptive procedure for nonlocal concrete damage models	Abdelhamid Becheur	Algeria	Submission 4636
Nokta Direnç Kaynaklı Benzer Olmayan 304 ve 430 Paslanmaz Çelik Birleşimlerinin Mekanik ve Mikroyapı Özelliklerinin İncelenmesi	Cihangir Tevfik Sezgin	Turkey	Submission 5474
Basma Deformasyonunun Düşük Yoğunluklu Polietilen Malzemelerin Mekanik ve Sertlik Özelliklerine Etkilerinin Araştırılması	Erkin Akdoğan and Mehmet Şahbaz	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 2629
Fructose dehydration reaction to 5-hydroxymethyl furfural over sulfonated carbons catalysts	Mahdi Achour and Fatima Ammari	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2762
Farklı Uzama Oranlarında Çekme İşlemi Uygulanmış Yüksek Yoğunluklu Polietilen Malzemelerin Mekanik Özelliklerinin Araştırılması	Mehmet Şahbaz and Erkin Akdoğan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 5383
IoT NETWORK SECURITY: THREATS AND ATTACK DETECTION	Hanan Abu Kwaider and Erdiñç Avaroğlu	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 9957
Locator Placement Optimization during Machining Turbine Blades Using Genetic Algorithm	Mustapha Arslane, Mohamed Slamani, Belkacem Aoufi and Jean-François Chatelain	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Canada	Submission 4644

Session 3.14		22 JULY 2022 13:00-14:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
A Simple Liquid Level Measurement Method Based on Fiber Bragg Gratings	Şerif Ali Sadık, Cengiz Yüksel and Fatih Koç	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 5982
Simple, Low-Cost and Non-invasive Liquid Level Sensor System Based on Ultrasonic Sensor	Şerif Ali Sadık, Oğuzhan Özen and Furkan Akçam	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1528
Determination of mechanical properties of Alumina-Zirconia ceramic composites by instrumented indentations.	Hocine Makri	Algeria	Submission 9038
RECOVERY OF RECYCLED FINES IN THE MANUFACTURE OF A NEW RANGE OF SAND CONCRETE	Ikram Souici, Leila Zeghichi and Abdelhalim Benouis	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 8378
COVID-19 Detection on Radiological Images with Deep Learning	Tanju Ceylan and Özkan İnik	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 7510
Isı Eşanjörlerinde Nanoakışkanların Kullanımı	Edip Taşkesen	Turkey	Submission 2747
Tolerance Analysis Using the Small Displacement Torsor Concept	Belkacem Aoufi, Hacene Ameddah, Mohamed Slamani and Mustapha Arslane	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 8320
Sabit Kanatlı Bir İnsansız Hava Aracının Konsept Tasarımı	Tarık ÜNLER, Tolunay DAĞ, Muhammet ÖZTÜRK	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	mail submission 13
Ağrının Ölçülmesi ve Ağrı Eşik Değerinin Belirlenmesi	Hakan Çağlar and Nihat Daldal	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 4918
The mechanical response of concrete made from recycled aggregates	Allal Meftah, Zeghichi Leila and Souici Ikram	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 8334

Session 3.15		22 JULY 2022 13:00-14:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Direct Torque Control of Dual Star Induction Motor using Grey Wolf Optimization Technique (GWO)	ZEMMIT Abderrahim, HARRAG Abdelghani, MESSALTI Sabir	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	mail submission 28
Activated Carbons Derived from Starch by Chemical Activation with K ₂ CO ₃ for Removal of Methylene Blue from Waters	Ömer Kazak	Turkey	Submission 9559
On the Deployment and Evaluation of Machine Learning Models to Improve Construction Management Practices	Mohamed Elmenshawy, Abobakr Al- Sakkaf and Eslam Mohammed Abdelkader	Canada, Canada, Egypt	Submission 5426
Comparative study of the surface mechanical properties of monocrystalline and polycrystalline ceramics	Salim Benaissa and Fouzia Chergui	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1308
Evaluation Of The Corrosion Inhibition Of C38 Carbon Steel By Polyvinyl Pyrrolidone In Different Aggressive Aqueous Media.	Salah Merah, Khalil Bouoka and Khadidja Hellal	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7543
LiF:Mg,Ti thermoluminescence kinetic parameters determination using computerized glow curve deconvolution (CGCD) technique and suitable trap model	Chahra-Zed Benkhelifa and Fayçal Kharfi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7278
A CRITICAL PART ANALYSIS FOR AN ARMED DRONE COMPANY	Abdurrahman Aytan, İlayda Coşansel and Ece Arzu Yildiz	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 0413
New ferromagnetic half-metallic perovskite TiMgO ₃ for spintronic application	Cheyma Boualleg and Athmane Meddour	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 8297
Silika Nanopartiküllerinin İlaç Salım Sistemlerinde Değerlendirilmesi	Hilal Erkan, Ceren Emîr, Cem Özel and Sevil YÜcel	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 7281
Amoxicillin Release From Poly(hydroxyethyl methacrylate-N-methacryloyl-(L)-glutamic acid) Cryogel Microdiscs	Kemal Çetin	Turkey	Submission 1288

Session 3.16		22 JULY 2022 14:00-15:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Sol-gel combined mecano-thermal synthesis of Y2O3, CeO2, and PdO partially coated ZnO for sulfamethazine and basic yellow 28 photodegradation under UV and visible light	Mohamed Belghiti and Tanji Karim	Morocco, Morocco	Submission 4365
Groundwater quality classification for irrigation purposes based on irrigation water quality index	Aymen Zegaar, Samira Ounoki and Abdelmoutia Telli	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 8120
Comparative study between elastomeric bridge bearing and pot bearing	Sidali Bahmani, Sohaib Harbi and Brahim Khalil Benazzouz	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 4097
Exponential stability of solutions to nonlinear time-varying delay systems of neutral type equations	Fatima Djeradi and Fares Yazid	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2057
Haplodrassus soerenseni (Strand, 1900) Türünün Sitogenetik Özelliklerinin Araştırılması	Ayşegül Aydın and Zübeyde Kumbıçak	Turkey	Submission 8773
Machine Learning Based Classification Algorithm for AP Selection in Cell-Free MIMO Systems	Mert Demirel and Esra Aycan Beyazıt	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 3913
Simulation-based Evaluation of Windows Opening Ratio Impact on Daylight Distribution of School Building under Hot and Dry Climate	Khaled Mansouri and Leila Sriti	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 6494
Evaluation of the antifungal activity of Mentha spicata and Foeniculum vulgare Mill. essential oils against Fusarium sp.	Merihane Gharzouli and Abdelhakim Aouf	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1268
PSO-Based CNN Hyperparameter Optimization for Lung Cancer Classification	Özgür Duran and Özkan İnik	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 0985
Python for Finance: Open Source Tools and Development of an Algorithmic Robot	Abdullah Öntürk, Mustafa Ulaş, Murat Karabatak and Yunus Santur	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 9912

Session 3.17		22 JULY 2022 14:00-15:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Baküde Badamdar Otoyolu-İsmayıl Qutqaşanlı Caddesinin Webster Yöntemiyle Ortalama Taşıt Gecikmelerinin Hesaplanması	Magsud Guliyev and Muhammed Milani	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 9028
An algorithm for continuous global optimization problems via space filling curves	Raouf Ziadi	Algeria	Submission 3762
CAN için Tersine Mühendislik Yaklaşımı	Esin Yavuz	Turkey	Submission 3921
Synthesis of novel benzothiazole chalcone derivatives: enzyme inhibition and theoretical studies	Ahmad Badreddin Musatat, Alparslan Atahan, Mustafa Zengin, Kübra Çıkrıkçı, Nahit Gençer	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	mail submission 15
Environmental Impacts of Emissions from Motor Vehicles	Eylem Yılmaz Ulu	Turkey	Submission 7089
SMOTE Aşırı Örnekleme Yönteminin Öğrenci Performans Tahminine Etkisi	SümeYra Muti, İsmet Abacı and Buket Doğan	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1484
Hayvan Taşımacılığında Stres Azaltma Etkilerinin İncelenmesi	Fakhri Nasibov and Muhammed Milani	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 6895
Makaslı Bir Kaldırma Platformunun Optimum Tasarımı, Analizi ve İmalatı	Murat Metehan Ekici and Ali Ozturk	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 8949
Effects of Exogenous Glycine Betaine on the Reduction of Drought Stress Damage in Two Wheat Varieties with Different Drought Tolerance	Sevgi DONAT, Okan ACAR	Turkey, Turkey	mail submission 16
Dinamik ve Statik Sistemde C. vulgaris Kültürünün Gelişim Özellikleri	Mehmet KALENDER, Abayhan BURAN	Turkey, Turkey	mail submission 17

Session 3.18		22 JULY 2022 14:00-15:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
THE ERROR DETECTION AND CORRECTION ABILITY FOR k-FIBONACCI CODING/DECODING METHOD	Öznur Öztunç Kaymak	Turkey	Submission 7603
Bir açık cevher ocağının nihai ve en uygun sınırlarının belirlenmesi	Liaqat Khezrawi, Bahadır Şengün and Bülent Erdem	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 7681
Anti-reflection properties of MgF ₂ single-layered mineral glass producing by TVA technique	Nihan Akkurt Özgür, Suat Pat, Betül Öztetik and Şadan Korkmaz	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 8795
The conjugation of the functionalized halloysite nanotubes and encapsulation by sodium alginate coatings for sustained drug delivery: pH-controlled release of drugs	Roufaida Merir and Milad Baitiche	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 3133
A Novel Method for Detection of Latent Fingermarks with Plant Extracts: A preliminary study	Barış Uzuncan and Kıymet Berkil Akar	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 4635
Numerical comparative study of mixed convection in air-based tubular cavity receiver of solar parabolic trough concentrator heated by uniform and non-uniform heat flux	Hassene Boutelis, Ammar Benderradji, Dalila Titouna and Lazher Serir	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7568
Data Mining in Finance: Concepts, Trend and Applications	Ahmet Tunahan Korkmaz, Mustafa Ulaş, Murat Karabatak and Yunus Santur	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 7467
Physico-chemical and mechanical characterization of the plant fiber stipa tenacissima extracted from HODNA region	Samira Bouchareb, Mansour Rokbi and Mohamed Benhamida	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 8752
Farklı Oranlarda Öğütülmüş Muz Lifi Takviyeli Polipropilen Kompozit Malzemenin Mekanik Özelliklerinin İncelenmesi	Akar Doğan	Turkey	Submission 2248
Investigation of thermal, optical and electrochemical properties of product obtained via oxidative polymerization of 4,4'-thiodianiline in aqueous alkaline medium	Elif Karacan Yeldir and İsmet Kaya	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 6955

Session 3.19		22 JULY 2022 15:00-16:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Synthesis and Structural Properties of Pyrazole and Thiopyrimidine Azo Dyes Derivated from 2nd and 3rd Position of Phenyl Ring	Gülnihal Erten, Aykut Demirçalı and Fikret Karıcı	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 9152
Effective control of glass-assisted CVD-grown MoS ₂ size distribution via surface patterning	Fikret Gonca Aras and Aydan Yeltik	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 6483
Potato genome editing with CRISPR/Cas9	Izdihar Ferhat and Boualem Harfi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2682
Development Of Fleet Tracking Systems Using Direct CAN Data	Ferhat Onat Şirin and Reyat Yılmaz	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 2841
SiC/AlSi7Mg2 METAL MATRİSLİ KOMPOZİTLERİN DELİNMESİNDE DELME PARAMETRELERİNİN KESME KUVVETİ, YÜZEY PÜRÜZLÜLÜĞÜ VE TALAŞ OLUŞUMU ÜZERİNDEKİ ETKİSİNİN ARAŞTIRILMASI	Ismail Erhan Kutsal, Yahya Hışman Çelik and Erol Kılıçkap	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 9123
Signature verification: the case of forgery by imitation	Boucerredj Leila, Kechroud Karima, Doghmane Hakim, Bennacer Layachi and Boulkenafet Imane	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 3377
Generalization of an Integer Sequence Associated with Tribonacci Numbers	Barış Arslan and Kemal Uslu	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 6715
A Literature Review on Smart Attendance Systems	Bawar Ali Abdalkarim Abdalkarim and Devrim Akgün	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 6549
Bulut Tabanlı Bir Mesajlaşma Uygulaması Tasarımı ve Gerçekleştirimi	Ceren Çelik, Semih Çakır and Nesibe Yalçın	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 3832
A Comparative Evaluation of the Performance of Three CNC Machine Tools	Mechta Ahlem, Slamani Mohamed, Zaoui Moussa and Chatelain Jean-François	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Canada	Submission 2405

Session 3.20		22 JULY 2022 15:00-16:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Dikey Kalkış ve İniş Yeteneğine Sahip Bir İnsansız Hava Aracının Çok Disiplinli Kavramsal Tasarımı	Dilara Nur Bektaş, Gamze Yaman, Tolunay Dağ and Tarık Ünler	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 2922
Detection of resistant pathogenic strains in poultry feed	Feryal Belfihadj, Anfal Kara, Meriem Elkolli and Naouel Boussualim	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1047
Pattern Analysis Framework for Financial Time Series	Üzeyir Aysel and Yunus Santur	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 4862
Determination of Anti-coronavirus Drug; Favipiravir in Pharmaceutical Formulations by Green HPLC Method	Melisa Pehlivan, Cem Ulaş and Şule Dinç Zor	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 0811
Mineralogical characterization of the Tizert copper deposit (Ighrem inlier, Morocco)	Kaoutar Dachri, Mohamed Hibti, Khalid El Amari and Khalid Naji	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 8626
İNSANSIZ HAVA ARACI KANADINDA RİB SAYISINDAKİ VE MALZEMESİNDEKİ DEĞİŞİME BAĞLI DEFORMASYONUN İNCELENMESİ	Nur YILDIRIM, Sakine KURTAR, Gizem BEDENLİ, Tolunay DAĞ, Muhammet ÖZTÜRK and Tarık ÜNLER	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 2440
Automatic Implant Detection Using Deep Learning	Halil İbrahim Kaya, Berrin Çelik and Mahmut Emin Çelik	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 8956
Structural, mineralogical and physico-chemical characterization of clays from the Missouri region in Morocco	Mohammed El Khalfaouy, El-Kaber Hachem and Mohammed Belghazdis	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 2049
Nanomaterial-Based Vaccination to Ameliorate the Challenges of Traditional Vaccination	Şeyda Yıldız and Yağmur Ünver	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 5732
Bacteriology Profile and Antibiotic Susceptibility Analyses of Pus Isolates from El-Eulma Hospital (Setif)	Anfal Kara, Feryal Belfihadj, Naouel Boussualim and Meriem Elkolli	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 6890

Session 3.21		22 JULY 2022 15:00-16:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Göz Hareketleri Temelli İnsan Bilgisayar Arabirimi	Recep Arslan and Selim Aras	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 0408
INVESTIGATION OF THE INTERFACIAL ADHESION BETWEEN JUTE FIBERS AND THE POLYMER MATRIX BY MICRO-BOND TESTS	Sidali Zernadji, Mohamed Benhamida and Mansour Rokbi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2719
Chemical composition and antioxidant activity of the essential oil of <i>Ononis angustissima</i> Lam. subsp. <i>filifolia</i> Murb endemic to the region of Biskra, Algeria	Messaoudi Khadidja, Benmeddour Tarek and Guido Flamini	Algeria, Algeria, Italy	Submission 4729
The application of systematic maintenance on rotating machinery	Lamia Benzaid, Toufik Sebbagh and Zina Azzez	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 4706
Effects of Modern AI Trends on Smart Farming to Boost Crop Yield	Muhammad Baballe Ahmad, Zaharadeen Yusuf Abdullahi, Amira Musa Saad, Salmanu Safiyanu Abdulsalam, Kassim Sulaiman Abubakar and Adamu Bello	Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria	Submission 1856
Voltammetric Determination of Tofacitinib with Calix[n]arene Modified Pencil Graphite Electrodes	Tuğba Sardohan Köseoğlu, Aykut Yalabık, Esengül Kır and Hasan Köseoğlu	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 9349
Modern İletken Yapıları Kullanılarak ENH Kayıplarının Azaltılması	Engin Kıran and Serhat Berat Efe	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 5568
<i>Zelotes metellus</i> (ROEWER, 1928) (ARANEAE: GNAPHOSIDAE) TÜRÜNÜN SİTOGENETİK ÖZELLİKLERİNİN ARAŞTIRILMASI	Eren Kahyaoğlu and Zübeyde Kumbıçak	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 4005
İNORGANİK FOSFAT ÇÖZÜCÜ ve BİTKİ BÜYÜMESİNİ TEŞVİK ETTİĞİ BİLİNEBİR BİR FUNGUSUN (<i>Aspergillus niger</i>) HIYAR BİTKİSİNİN (<i>Cucumis sativus</i> L.), BÜYÜME ve GELİŞİMİ ÜZERİNE ETKİSİ	Kağan Veryer, Mehmet Nuri Aydoğan and Murat Özdal	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 3275
<i>ZELOTES SEGREGEX</i> (SIMON, 1878) (ARANEAE: GNAPHOSIDAE) TÜRÜNÜN SİTOGENETİK ÖZELLİKLERİNİN ARAŞTIRILMASI	Nilay Kolcan and Zübeyde Kumbıçak	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 5647

Session 3.22		22 JULY 2022 16:00-17:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Phytochemicals as an alternative bioresource for the prevention of UV radiations	Yousra Touami and Rafik Marir	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 5322
KBRN TEHDİDİ ÜZERİNE TÜRKİYE'DE YAPILAN TEZLER VE WEB OF SCİENCE (WOS) VERİ TABANI'NDAKİ ÇALIŞMALARA BİBLİYOGRAFİK BAKIŞ	Ümüő Sarpkaya, Mehmet Eyyuphan Yakıncı	Turkey	Submission 0957
Development and Design of Biogas Generation System Plant for Treatment of Ribbed Smoked Sheet Effluent	Emmanuel Fagbemi, Nyakno Udokpoh, Andrew Ohifuemen, Olatunde Ibikunle and Evelyn Musa	Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria	Submission 8937
First-principles study of structural, electronic and optical properties of double half-Heusler alloy :Ta ₂ FeNiSn ₂	Berarma Khadidja and Sâad Essaoud Saber	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7381
RUBBERIZED CONCRETE PRODUCTION – A REVIEW	Emmanuel Fagbemi, Nyakno Udokpoh, Andrew Ohifuemen and Olatunde Ibikunle	Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria	Submission 2165
Electrical and Mechanical Properties of Natural Rubber Composites	Tuba Evgin, Matej Mičušík, Ivan Chodak and Maria Omastova	Turkey, Slovakia, Slovakia, Slovakia	Submission 7462
Farm Automation with Iot	Benelmir Okba and Dhiabi Fathi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 9805
Farklı Cinsiyet ve Yaş Aralıkları İçin Derin Öğrenme Tabanlı İrk Sınıflandırma	Asuman Günay Yılmaz and Ömer Kökçe	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 3146
The detection of extremely toxic gases on a two-dimensional platform based on a resonator based on photonic crystals	Mehdi Ghoumazi and Mourad Bella	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 3418
Modeling and Simulation of Single and Triple Junction Solar Cell Using PyAMS	Dhiabi Fathi, Benelmir Okba and Saadoune Achour	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 3134

Session 3.23		22 JULY 2022 16:00-17:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
controllability of fractional degenerate singular problem	Achab Fatma and Rezzoug Imad	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 6688
GRU ve CNN Tabanlı Hibrit Derin Öğrenme Modeli ile Çok Etiketli Metin Analizi	Halit Çetiner	Turkey	Submission 7052
PSO Based MPPT System For Fuel Cell	Seyit Alperen Çeltek	Turkey	Submission 3055
Performance Enhancement of Compact Terahertz Antenna Based on Defected Ground and Photonic Crystals Structure	Mohamed Nasr Eddine Temmar, Abdesselam Hocini, Djamel Khedrouche and Mohamed Elamine Benlakehal	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 8667
Selecting the best Machine Learning Approach for Predictive Maintenance using q-Rung Orthopair Fuzzy Complex Proportional Assessment method	Adem Pınar	Turkey	Submission 9131
Exponential Growth of Solution for a System of semilinear reaction diffusion Equations with Memories and Source Terms	Wissem Boughamsa and Amar Ouaoua	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2168
The Role of Urban Morphology in Flow characteristics and pollutant concentrations and distribution	Lamia Ben Ramoul	Algeria	Submission 0892
LSTM Based Text Classification for Turkish News	Özlem Feyza Erkan and Onur Cihan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 8229
Evaluation of In Vitro Genotoxic Effect of E-122 Carmoisine, Food Coloring, on Human Lymphocytes by Comet Assay	Sadriye Gökçe Kara, Deniz Yüzbaşıoğlu, Ece Avuloğlu Yılmaz and Fatma Ünal	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 3330
An Improved Grey Wolf Optimizer for Parameter Extraction of Photovoltaic Cells	Elmamoune Halassa, Abdellatif Seghiour, Lakhdar Mazouz, Aissa Chouder and Said Benkaihou	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 5646

Session 3.24		22 JULY 2022 16:00-17:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Faz Deđiřtiren Malzeme Kullanılan Isıl Enerji Depolama Sistemlerinde Akıřkan Giriř Sıcaklıđının Deđiřiminin Isı Transfer Performansı Üzerine Olan Etkilerinin Deneysel Olarak İncelenmesi	Eray Zađlanmıř and Tolga Demircan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 8328
Corrosion and biocompatibility behavior of Ti6Al4V in SBF solution in the presence of bioactivity thin film and Gentamicin antibiotic	Karima Boudjeda, Djihane Khalfi, Nassereddine Béliardouh and Khokha Lalaoui	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 3383
AA5754-H22/Zn/AA2024-T3 LEVHALARIN SÜRTÜNME KARIřTIRMA EKSTRÜZYON BİRLEřTİRMESİ	Nesliřah Kurnaz, Berna Salvazlıođlu and Yahya Bozkurt	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 8094
Numerical simulation of the explosion flow field and acoustic attenuation in gun suppressor	Ezedin Ayaliew Yimam and Tolga Demircan	Ethiopia, Turkey	Submission 9043
Removal of organic pollutants through innovative advanced oxidation techniques.	Rahma Benyahia and Ilhem Ghodbane	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 0893
A Review of Topological Graphs	Zainab Najı Hameed and Hiyam Kadhem	Iraq, Iraq	Submission 3378
Iris recognition based on the fusion of learned and handcrafted features	Abderrahmane Herbadji, Djamel Hebadji, Noubel Guermat and Lahcene Ziet	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 0502
Biosorption of malachite green using waste cotton seed <i>Gossypium arboreum</i>	Sabrina Oulad Brahim, Marwa Lamise Hamel, Yasmina Khane and Ilias Baba Arbi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 3580
<i>Gossypium arboreum</i> cotton-seed waste oil biodiesel production by esterification.	Marwa Lamise Hamel, Sabrina Ouled Brahim, Yasmina Khane and Ilias Baba Arbi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2222
Roma Dönemi Madeni Paralarının Derin Öđrenme Tabanlı Sınıflandırılması	Asuman Günay Yılmaz, Çiđdem Saygılı and Vasif Nabiyev	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 6031

Session 3.25		22 JULY 2022 17:00-18:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
A Survey on Ditopological Texture Spaces	Zainab Hameed and Hiyam Kadhem	Iraq, Iraq	Submission 4972
Toxicity Identification Using The Neural Network Algorithms	Sema Demirci Uzun, Vahide Bulut and Aytuğ Onan	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 8783
Role of Temperature on Structural, Optical and Electrical properties of Spray Pyrolysis CuO Thin Films	Ouarda Benmessaoud, Abdelouahab Ouahab, Sàad Rahmane, Hafida Attouche and Boutheina Saadi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7745
Effect of molar concentrations of zinc acetate on optical and structural properties of zinc oxide	Hafida Attouche and Ouarda Benmessaoud	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2060
New generalisation of the dynamic results in fixed point theorems in complet Metric space	Besma Laouadi, Leila Ben Aoua and Taki Eddine Oussaeif	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 6629
Sinterability and structural properties of magnesia-kaolinite ceramics.	Hadda Rezzag, Alima Mebrek and Sabrina Ladjma	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 5053
Electronic structure of the layered LiFeO2 studied by DFT+DMFT calculations	Soumia Bendhafer, Kamel Zanat and Kamel Zanat	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7564
Discovery of Novel Pyridine and Pyrimidinone Derivatives as Promising Antibacterial Agents	Stiti Mohamed Zakaria, Habila Tahir and Bouhedja Mourad	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 6782
A Simple, Efficient and Eco-Friendly Synthesis of 3,4-dihydropyrimidin-2(1H)-ones by Kaolin Under Solvent-Free Condition	Stiti Mohamed Zakaria, Khaled Khaled Ammar and Khelili Smail	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 4957
Influence of resin bed configuration on the electrodeionization (EDI) performance	Aicha Lakehal	Algeria	Submission 2813

Session 3.26		22 JULY 2022 17:00-18:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Elektrik İletim ve Dağıtım Hatlarındaki Teknik Enerji Kayıplarının İncelenmesi	Behçet Kocaman	Turkey	Submission 1490
Wi-Fi 2.4 GHz and 5 GHz Dual Band Antenna Design for IoT Based Smart Media Application	Derin Arda Şahin and Adnan Kaya	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 7082
Effects of Salinity on Seed germination and early seedling stage of durum wheat (Triticum Durum Desf.)	Fatima Hiouani, Rania Afif, Ouahiba Boukhrouf, Hichem Aissaoui and Naima Mebrek	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2940
Evaluating the durability properties and quality of concrete prepared with waste fine and coarse recycled brick aggregates	Mohammed Khattab, Samya Hachemi and Hicham Benzetta	Jordan, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 4969
Elektrikli Araçların Batarya Yönetim Sisteminin Soğutma Sistem Tasarımı ve Kontrolü	Murat Toren, Hakki Mollahasanoglu and Salih Muhsin Kaya	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 4035
Optimization of patch shape and size in mixed mode	Sidi Mohamed Fekih, Salma Aminallah and Boualem Attout	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 4184
Optimization of mechanical and geometrical properties of a composite patch adhesive	Salma Aminallah, Sidi Mohamed Fekih and Boualem Attout	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 3020
Identification of individuals by handwritten signature	Kechroud Karima and Boucerredj Leila	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 6092
Online signature verification using Teager-Huang Transform (THT)	Kechroud Karima and Boucerredj Leila	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7076
DETECTION OF ALGERIAN HONEY TYPES BY RAMAN SPECTROSCOPY USING FACTORIAL DISCRIMINANT ANALYSIS	Samir Cherigui, Ilyas Chikhi, Fayçal Dergal, Naziha Chabane and Nouredine Choukcou Braham	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1535

Session 3.27		22 JULY 2022 17:00-18:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
DETECTION OF HONEY ADULTERATION BY RAMAN SPECTROSCOPY USING K-MEANS CHEMOMETRIC METHOD	Samir Cherigui, Ilyas Chikhi and Fayçal Dergal	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2601
A Compact Crossover Design for Butler Matrix Feeding Network in 5G Sub 6GHz Wireless Applications	Gudrat Heydarli and Merih Palandoken	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 9824
Fotovoltaik Bir Sistem İçin Aynı Güçte Farklı Özelliklere Sahip İnverterlerin Karşılaştırmalı Analizi	Muhammet Raşit Sancar	Turkey	Submission 8822
Muğla İlinde Kurulacak Bir Güneş Enerjisi Santrali İçin Simülasyon Çalışması	Muhammet Raşit Sancar	Turkey	Submission 4446
Sabit ve Güneş Takip Sistemine Sahip İki Farklı Fotovoltaik Sistem İçin Karşılaştırmalı Analiz	Muhammet Raşit Sancar	Turkey	Submission 6618
A Systematic Investigation of Smart Home Automation Systems: Review	Abdulkadir Shehu Bari, Ibrahim Umar Tofa, Muhammad Abubakar Falalu, Muhammad Auwal Umar, Yakubu Yunusa Sulaiman, Abdullahi Mansur Gambale and Muhammad Baballe Ahmad	Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria	Submission 9488
EARNED VALUE MANAGEMENT (EVM) ANALYSIS IN CONTEXT OF TRIPLE CONSTRAINTS FOR A REAL-LIFE CONSTRUCTION PROJECT	Zeeshan Abbas, Muhammad Danish, Mir Alam, Sammar Abbas Shah and Abdul Qadeer	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Paksitan	Submission 3577
IMPLEMENTATION OF LEAN CONSTRUCTION IN CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY OF PAKISTAN	Zeeshan Abbas, Muhammad Danish, Mir Alam, Sammar Abbas Shah and Abdul Qadeer	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Paksitan	Submission 5410
VIRTUAL CONSTRUCTION PLANNING OF A CONSTRUCTION PROJECT USING BIM INNOVATIONS	Zeeshan Abbas, Sammar Abbas Shah, Abdul Qadeer and Arslan Amjid	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 7520
Optimisation of an adequate configuration of resisting frame reinforced concrete buildings using different column shapes	Imane Djafar Henni, M'Hamed Adjoudj and Karim Azzouz	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 0179

Session 4.1		23 JULY 2022 9:00-10:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Yapı Üzerindeki Bozulma ve Nem Hasarının Dijital Görüntü İşleme Yöntemi ile Tespiti	Saltuk Taha Ustaoglu and Betül Bektaş Ekici	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 9753
Su kaynaklı Caputo tipinde fraksiyonel bir salgın hastalık modelinin kararlılık analizi	Cemil Büyükdalı	Turkey	Submission 5759
Parçalı sabit argümanlı Conformable tipinde fraksiyonel bir Lasota Wazewska modelinin kararlılığı	Cemil Büyükdalı	Turkey	Submission 3388
Biochar-production, modification and application for water, waste water and soil remediation: review	Zulaikha Saeed and Muhammed Rizwan	Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 8533
Energy optimization by new algorithm P&O MPPT Techniques for photovoltaic systems	Boucerredj Leila, Griouz Badreddine, Moussaoui Abdelkrim and Debbache Nasreddine	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 4212
Systematic Study on the Challenges and Impacts of Automatic Watering Systems	Aliyu Hassan Muhammad, Abdulrahman Yusuf Abdullahi, Kassim Sulaiman Abubakar, Ibrahim Umar Tofa, Ibrahim Abba and Muhammad Baballe Ahmad	Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria	Submission 5372
Determination of in vitro antibacterial effects of selected washing solutions against foodborne pathogens	Ömer Faruk Celik	Turkey	Submission 2610
YOLOv5-based Vehicle Objects Detection Using UAV Images	Zeynep Nur Duman, Müzeyyen Büşra Çulcu and Oguzhan Katar	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 4087
EFFICIENCY ASSESSMENT OF MOZAMBICAN BANKING SECTOR USING DATA ENVELOPMENT ANALYSIS	Narciso Alfaiate and Yaprak Özdemir	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 3576
Design Approaches on Inner Bodies of Gears With Methods Topology Optimization and Lattice Structures	Behlül Becergen, Murat Çakmak, Muhammed Fatih Maral, Ahmet Dayanç and Feridun Karakoç	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 7977

Session 4.2		23 JULY 2022 9:00-10:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Örgütsel Adaletin İş Gören Motivasyonuna Etkisi: Doğrusal ve Yapay Sinir Ağları Modelleri ile Bir Uygulama	Akın Erdemir, Fatih Seyran and Tuğrul Batırer	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 7962
ENZİM TABANLI GAZ SENSÖR ÜRETİMİ VE UYGULAMALARI	Murat Evyapan and Deniz Ege Deniz	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 6511
Farklı Dolgu Tipleri için Çerçevelerin İtme Analizi ile Kıyaslanması	İbrahim BARAN KARAŞIN ve Mehmet Emin Öncü	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1614
Machine Learning Based Antenna Array Beamforming	Muhammed Uğur Kılıç and Özgür Tamer	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1557
AN IN SILICO STUDY: DETERMINATION OF POTENTIAL ANTI-INFLUENZA AGENTS BY VIRTUAL SCREENING AND MOLECULAR DOCKING	Alper Önder	Turkey	Submission 2994
Estimation of the Effect of Compression Pressure on Green Density of Al-Cu Alloy with ANFIS Model	Demet Zalaoglu and Pınar Karakuş	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1680
Effect of different thickness on structural, electrical and optical properties of sprayed oxide (Cr2O3) thin films	Saadi Boutheina, Saâd Rahmane and Ouarda Ben Messaoud	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1829
Corrosion resistance of multilayered coatings in biological environment	Raid Bahi, Chems Eddine Ramoul, Nasser Eddine Beliardouh, Karima Boudjeda and Corrine Nouveau	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 8477
Tribological performances of multilayered coatings in biological environment	Raid Bahi, Chems Eddine Ramoul, Karima Boudjeda, Nasser Eddine Beliardouh and Corinne Nouveau	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, France	Submission 6490
Bioethanol Dehydration with an Enhanced Cellulose Triacetate/Zinc Oxide Pervaporation Membrane.	Muhammad Nabeel Khaliq, Meshal Alzaid, Shahid Mehmood, Rizwan Ahmed Malik and Muddassir Ali	Pakistan, SA, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan,	Submission 3545

Session 4.3		23 JULY 2022 9:00-10:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Trichoderma As A Potential Bio-Repellent For Carpet Beetles	Serdar Bilginturan and Melis Bilginturan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 3445
Electrical-Optical improvement properties by inserting materials in organic solar cells	Chahrazed Bendenia, Hanaa Merad-Dib, Souhila Bendenia, Yamina Sefir and Baghdad Hadri	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1736
Control Modelling of Coupled Shell and Tube Heat Exchangers using Combined Neural Network and Fuzzy Logic	Moses Petinrin, Olusola Oke, Adedayo Adebayo, Olumide Towoju and Olawale Ismail	Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria	Submission 6219
Grenadine bark extract as a Green Corrosion Inhibitor for AISI 316 steel.	Amira Gharbi and Youcef Hamlaoui	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 9544
Effect of salinity on the germination of some varieties of quinoa (Chenopodium Quinoa Willd.)	Fatima Hiouani, Hichem Aissaoui, Naima Mebrek, Wahiba Boukhelouf and Hayet Derradji	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 4211
Effect of salt stress on bean germination (Phaseolus vulgaris L).	Fatima Hiouani, Hichem Aissaoui, Naima Mebrek, Wahiba Boukhelouf and Safa Bassou	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 6759
The effect of salt stress on germination and some growth parameters in four cumin varieties	Fatima Hiouani, Hichem Aissaoui, Naima Mebrek, Wahiba Boukhelouf and Asma Belal	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 4202
Effect of salt stress on germination and some growth parameters in some varieties of durum wheat and soft wheat	Fatima Hiouani, Hichem Aissaoui, Naima Mebrek, Wahiba Boukhelouf and Chaima Saker	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1976
OPTIMIZED ROUTE MODELLING OF SUSTAINABLE INSTITUTIONAL TRANSPORTATION SYSTEM	Sameer Zafar, Abdus Samad Farooq, Zahid Ullah Khan and Dr.Usman Farooqi	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 0641
Assessment of the Hole Quality During Drilling Alfa Fiber (Stipa tenacissima) Reinforced Composites	Madani Grine, Mohamed Slamani, Mustapha Arslane and Jean-François Chatelain	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Canada	Submission 8356

Session 4.4		23 JULY 2022 10:00-11:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Forest Fires: Challenges and Impact Review	Abdulkadir Shehu Bari, Aminu Abba, Muhammad Abubakar Falalu, Kassim Sulaiman Abubakar, Muhammad Auwal Umar, Muhammad Baballe Ahmad and Yusuf Idris Muhammad	Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria, Nigeria	Submission 6083
Analysis and Design of Terahertz Slot Antenna Based on Photonic Crystal Substrate	Mohamed Nasr Eddine Temmar, Abdesselam Hocini, Djamel Khedrouche and Mohamed Elamine Benlakehal	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 6234
COMPARISON OF SEISMIC PERFORMANCE OF RC FRAME STRUCTURE WITH AND WITHOUT SOIL-STRUCTURE INTERACTION (SSI)	Haider Masaud and Iqbal Ahmad	Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 6928
Improve performance of suspect detection system by Netlogo and enhance security	Aggabou Loubna, Lakehal Brahim and Mouda Mouhamed	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 8781
Effective adsorption of Diclofenac antibiotic using biochar derived from pepper stem	Naima Azri, Ammar Fadel, Abdelkader Ouakouak and Rachid Chebbi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 0689
DDoS Attack Detection on SDN with Conv1D and LSTM	Alperen Orsdemir, Hamidullah Nazari and Devrim Akgun	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 2587
New hosts and parasitism note for the mite Leptus (Trombidiformes, Erythraeidae) associated with solitary wasp family Sphecidae (Insecta, Hymenoptera)	İlyas Can	Turkey	Submission 7744
Optimization of Roller Burnishing Process Using Bees and Genetic Algorithm	Mevlüt Aydın, Mevlüt Türköz, Abdullah Çakan and Mete Kalyoncu	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 2072
Human Activity Recognition Identification with Tuned Machine Learning Algorithms	Akın Özçift	Turkey	Submission 6481

Session 4.5		23 JULY 2022 10:00-11:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Antioxidant activity of Green synthesis of Magnesium oxide nanoparticles using fresh and dry plant extracts of Pelargonium graveolens from southern Algeria	Maroua Boudraa, Yasmina Khane and Hamed Bokhari	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 5510
Traveling wave solutions for the mKdV-ZK equation by using the generalized $\exp(-\varphi(\xi))$ -expansion method	Riadh Hedli and Fella Berrimi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 5180
İçerisine Yerleştirilen Elipsin Kavitede Meydana Gelen Birleşik Doğal ve Zorlanmış Taşımına Etkisi	Nazım Kurtulmuş	Turkey	Submission 8461
Polymer-based Biosensors: From Biofunctional Surfaces to Point-of-Care Biodevices	Emine Güler Celik	Turkey	Submission 3621
Existence results for subcritical and critical p-fractional elliptic equations via Nehari manifold method	Djamel Abid	Algeria	Submission 7548
Theoretical study of laser-water interaction in fs time regime	Amal Zerradi, Ahmed Abdelmalek and Zeyneb Bedrane	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2708
Optimization of energy density in supercapacitors by utilizing Artificial Neural Network-Genetic Algorithm hybrid model	Betül Uralcan	Turkey	mail submission 26
Study of the Phase transition in a mixed hadronic-QCD colorless plasma system from entropy evolution	Bachir Moussaoui and Amal Ait El Djoudi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 3596
Effect of MgO on the properties and microstructure of a synthetic mullite	Fouzia Chargui and Salim Benaissa	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1821
Technological performance of an indigenous lactic flora isolated from an artisanal cheese from western Algeria "J'ben of Sfisifa" based on milk from Hamra sheep	Mostefa Medjahed and Abdelkader Elamine Dahou	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 9387
INVESTIGATIVE ASSESSMENT OF GEOLOGICAL LOCATION ON ENERGY CONSUMPTION PATTERNS OF A MODREN BUILDING	Rehan Asif, Adnan Anwar, Hamza Tanvir, Talha Bin Tahir and Syed Shujaa Safdar	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 2205
Anaerobik Gut Fungusları ile Laktik asit bakterilerinin kokültür olarak yetiştirildiklerinde Enzim Aktiviteleri Üzerine Etkileri	Tuğçe Turgut, Aziz Bolat and Halit Yücel	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 8291

Session 4.6		23 JULY 2022 10:00-11:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Contribution to the study and modeling of the ozone generators by cylindrical dielectric barrier discharge	Rachida. Hedara	Algeria	mail submission 27
Design Optimization of a Bracket Plate for an Ammunition Feed Mechanism of a Medium Caliber Cannon	Cihan Turan and Hacı Abdullah Taşdemir	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 6578
Finite Element Analysis of ARALL Composites by Using LS-DYNA Software	Uzay Gezer, Yusuf Kepir, Bünyamin Demir, Memduh Kara and Alper Günöz	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 2279
A Multi-criteria Decision Making based Solution to Greening Strategies through VUCA Analysis for EFB Batteries	Özge Özusta and Burcu Yılmaz Kaya	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 8314
A comparative study of the removal of prednisolone and ibuprofen on activated carbon from aqueous medium	Meriem Chebbi, Samira Ounoki and Lila Youcef	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 0322
Photocatalytic degradation of the emergent pollutant metronidazole in water using HMS-supported cobalt under UV irradiation	Djelloudi Thiziri, Zekri Ouardia and Touahra Fouzia	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2030
Citrus limon (L.) zest aqueous extract mediated bioactive silver nanoparticles: characterization and biological activity.	Sofiane Khane, Yasmina Khane, Fares Fenniche, Djaber Aouf and Khadidja Benouis	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 9575
Geometrical system parameters effect on the electric field and potential using GTAW process	Samira Benharat, Dyhia Doufene and Leila Belgacem	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 8463
Kurumsal Envanter Yönetim Sistemi için Ontoloji Tabanlı Yaklaşım	Ozgu Can and Elif Ezgi Emre	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 2593
Geotextile Applications and Innovation in Geotechnical Engineering: A Review	Srijan Srijan and Ashok Kumar Gupta	India, India	Submission 3891
GEOTECHNICAL APPLICATIONS OF SEWAGE SLUDGE STABILIZED WITH BIOMASS ASH AND ITS EFFECT ON SOIL NUTRIENTIAL PROPERTIES	Ishowriya Yumnam	India	Submission 4205

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TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Isı Geçirgenlik Katsayısına Göre Isı Kaybının Belirlenmesi: SDÜ Mühendislik Fakültesi Örneği	Serdar Mustafa GÜMÜŞBAŞ and Barış GÜREL	Turkey, Turkey	mail submission 29
On the integral automorphism of quadratic forms	Ketevan Shavgulidze and Lika Svanadze	Georgia, Georgia	Submission 6269
Evaluation Total Quality Management in terms of Sustainability: A Health Facility Example	Ayşenur Erdil	Turkey	Submission 8301
Sustainability of Reverse Logistics and Green Supply Chain: A Case Study	Ayşenur Erdil	Turkey	Submission 4174
EMG Sinyalleri Kullanılarak Yapay Sinir Ağı ile Hastalık Teşhisi	Nadide Gülşah Gülenç	Turkey	Submission 9369
Transport AC Loss Analysis of MRI Main Magnet System Designed from REBCO HTS Tapes	Hüsnü Kara and Fedai İnanır	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 7409
Analysis of offshore wind turbine towers with different types of buoys in linear wave action by finite element method	Fethi Şermet, Muhammed Ensari Yiğit and Melih Yıldız	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 6740
Susceptibility Assessment of Structures at El Kherba "Mila" due to the Effects of Earthquake and Landslide 2020	Hosni Abderrahmane Taleb and Ismahene Guemidi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 5579
An Alternative for Hybrid Vehicles: Six-Stroke Engines	Muhammed Akar, Emre Arabacı and Bayram Kılıç	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 3756
Elastic properties of layered LiCoO ₂ and LiFeO ₂	Ahmed Boufelfel	Algeria	Submission 1663
Influence of increasing order of AVR machine on electrical grid stability	Taha Rachdi, Yahia Saoudi, Ines Mahmoud and Ayachi Errachdi	Tunisia, Tunisia, Tunisia, Tunisia	Submission 4900
İKİ BOYUTLU MALZEMELERİN BAZI ÖZELLİKLERİNİN İNCELENMESİ	Betul Öztetik and Şadan Korkmaz	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 5347
Electro-Mechanic Analysis of 1.5 T MRI Magnets Designed from 2G HTS Tapes	Husnu Kara and Fedai İnanır	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 0762
Effect of hemp and glass fibers on the physical and mechanical behavior of polymer-based repair mortars	Meriem Dridi, Samya Hachemi and Ahmed Abderraouf Belkadi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1942

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TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Design of a system of photocatalytic reactors in series for the degradation of the reactive black 5 dye under visible light	Elizabeth Rojas, Marco Antonio Cortez Jiménez, Arendy Lucia Escobar García and Richard S. Ruiz Martínez	Mexico, Mexico, Mexico, Mexico	Submission 1274
Experimental study on shear behavior of sand mixed with marble powder	Sidali Denine, Missoum Benziane Mehdi, Nadhir Toubal Seghir and Yassine Abbas	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2271
Dielectric characterization of the epoxy resin in a rectangular waveguide at 9.490 GHz.	Labiba Chioukh, Nacerdine Bouzit and Rabah Delfouf	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2717
Analysis of an Electromagnetic Energy Harvester for Different Incident Wave Polarization and Loads	Muhammed Said Boybay and Sadık Zuhur	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 2652
Biyosensörler ve Ülkemizde Biyosensörler Üzerine Yapılan Çalışmalar	Tugba Karayigit, Yasemin Gündoğdu, Hamdi Şükür KILIÇ, and Serap Yigit Gezgin	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 2589
Prediction of peak strength for square and rectangular concrete columns confined with CFRP wraps	Nadia Diboune, Riad Benzaid and Mohammed Berradia	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 9691
Effect of Mo doping on physical properties of ZnO thin films prepared by jet nebulizer spray pyrolysis technique	Noubeil Guermat, Warda Darenfad, Kamel Mirouh and Abderrahmane Herbadji	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1825
Accuracy Comparison of CNN Networks on GTSRB Dataset	Gökberk Ay, Akif Durdu and Barış Samim Nesimioğlu	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 8468
İletişim ve Radar Dalga Sinyallerinin Zaman-Frekans Analizi ve Evrişimli Sinir Ağları Kullanılarak Sınıflandırılması	Esra ERGİN, Umut ÖZKAYA	Turkey, Turkey	mail submission 30
Water surface profiles visual assessment and numerical validation in an open channel through a tilting flume	Adeer Khan, Abbas Ali Shah and Usman Hussain	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 1822

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TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
AN IMPROVED BERNSSEN ALGORITHM STEPS FOR TURKISH LICENSE PLATE NUMBER RECOGNITION USING ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORK	Cafer Bal, Auwal Salisu Yunusa, Nuhu A. Muhammad, Mariya G. Mustapha	Nigeria, Turkey	Submission 9389
Traditional and Modern Methods for Extraction of Plant-Based Bioactive Compounds	Pınar Gümüş	Turkey	Submission 2645
Özel kafa formuna sahip bir vidanın üretim aşamalarının analizi	Güldenur Ham and Eser Yazar	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 0625
A Simple Approach for designing real-life open channel structures with the help of water surface profile generation in a tilting flume	Arshad Ali, Haider Ilyas and Usman Hussain	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 4438
Worker fatigue detection system with the aid of deep learning method	M. Emin Şahin	Turkey	Submission 0134
NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION OF LOW-VELOCITY IMPACT RESPONSE OF CARBON/GLASS EPOXY COMPOSITES	Yusuf Kepir, Uzun Gezer, Bünyamin Demir, Memduh Kara and Alper Günöz	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 8732
Multi-Class Turkish Sentiment Analysis Using Machine Learning Algorithms	Gizem Gümüşçekeçici and Ayşe Berna Altinel	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 8644
Sürdürülebilirlik Raporlarının Tedarik Zinciri Yönetimi Açısından İncelenmesi	Beste Desticioğlu Taşdemir	Turkey	Submission 4744
Yenilenebilir Enerji Kaynakları ile Desteklenen Akıllı Şebekelerde Elektrikli Araç Şarj İstasyonları İçin Enerji Yönetimi	Said Yayla and Engin Özdemir	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 2197
The weak solution of an antiplane contact problem for electro-elastic materials with short memory	Besma Fadlia and Mohamed Dalah	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2450
Control and Performance Improvements of Piezoelectric Inertia Friction	Samia Latreche, Mabrouk Khemliche and Samira Boumous	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7291
Optimal Integration of DGs Based Renewable Energy in Radial Distribution System Using GA, PSO and GWO	Belkacem Mahdad and Hasni Haroune	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1229

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Influencing parameters on 13Cr5Ni2Mo Super- Martensitic Stainless Steel coefficient of friction behaviour	Khokha Lalaoui, Mounia Belaid and Beliardouh Nasser Eddine	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 2434
Sol gel of Al doped ZnO thin films: preparation and characterization	Sarra Berra, Abdelhafid Mahroug and Samir Hamrit	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 6625
Assessment of Current Domestic Water Supply and Unmet Demand for Karachi City on WEAP For Future Water Resources Management	Umara Khan, Awad Nawaz and Muhammad Waqas Malik	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 6632
Sparger type influence on the Residence Time Distribution of a D-shape Airlift loop reactor	Amine Berouaken, Nacereddine Moudoud and Rachida Rihani	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1667
The Effect Of Soil-Structure Interaction On The Dynamic Response Of Adjacent Structures	Ikhlasse Kheira Asmouni and Mohammed Mekki	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 5755
Structural, Magnetic, Elastic and Electronic properties of KMgNSe alloy: first principles study	Houssam Meghchouche and Malika Labidi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 8843
Numerical Study of a cantilever Sheet Pile Wall Behavior	Ilham Bahloul, Lazhar Belabed and F. Zohra Benamara	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 5332
Study of various design techniques of millimeter-wave antennas for 5G devices and IoT	Shazia Ashraf, Javaid A Sheikh and Ayash Ashraf	India, India, India	Submission 8971
EVALUATION OF LEAD REMOVAL FROM DRAINAGE WATER OF THE ZAB EL-GHARBI AREA. BISKRA Provence	Masmoudi Toufik, Benakcha Mansoura and Guergazi Saadia	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 9137
SOME PROPERTIES OF (n, m)-POWER-HYPONORMAL IN SEMI HILBERTIAN SPACE	Cherifa Chellali	Algeria	Submission 7527
The effect of bio-synthesized ZnO nanoparticles on X60 steel corrosion in 1M HCl and bacteria	Sihem Abderrahmane, Sarah Messast, Nabila Bouasla, Sameh Athmani and Karima Abderrahim	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 9074
The mechanical response of concrete made from recycled aggregates	Allal Meftah, Zeghichi Leila and Souici Ikram	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7822

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Comparative studies of undoped/Ni-doped/Zn-doped/F-doped SnO ₂ transparent conducting oxide thin films	Warda Darenfad, Noubel Guermat and Kamel Mirouh	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 6980
Local analysis of a competitive problem with toxicants	Nihal Özdoğan	Turkey	mail submission 31
Çok Ölçekli Temel Bileşen Analizi ve Evrimsel Sınır Ağları ile Elektrokardiyografi Sinyallerinden Miyokart Enfarktüsünün Tespiti	Arda Aydoğan, Buse İçme, Ali İnce, Sümeyya Arıkan and Fatma Latifoğlu	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1361
Epilepsi Tespitinde Gürbüz Yerel Ortalama Ayırışım ve Ampirik Kip Ayırışım Yöntemlerinin Performans Analizi	Oğuzkaan Çatalkaya, Tuba Hazman, Sabrina Turturova, Tuğba Şentürk and Fatma Latifoğlu	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1118
Makashlı Bir Kaldırma Platformunun Optimum Tasarımı, Analizi ve İmalatı	Murat Metehan Ekici and Ali Öztürk	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 8949
Classification of Raisin Grains Using Some Artificial Intelligence Methods	Selim Güvenç, Yavuz Ünal, Hüsamettin Kaplan, Yusuf Bektaş and Muhammed Bedirhan Çağlar	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 2470
Ortopedideki Yük Taşıyıcı Uygulamalar İçin Co ve Cr Elementlerinden Arındırılmış TiN Duplex Yüzey Kaplamaların Aşınma Özelliklerinin İncelenmesi	Yenal Vangözü	Turkey	Submission 3221
Metaheuristic FIR Filter Design with Multi-Objective Atomic Orbital Search Algorithm	Mehmet Fatih Karakaş and Fatma Latifoğlu	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 3032
ARAZİ TİPİ GÜNEŞ ENERJİ SANTRALLERİNİN VERİMLİLİK ANALİZİ: KONYA ÖRNEĞİ	Bahadır Asma and Levent Seyfi	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 6876
ÇATI ÜSTÜ GÜNEŞ ENERJİ SANTRALLERİNDE VERİMLİLİĞİ ETKİLEYEN FAKTÖRLERİN BELİRLENMESİ	Himmat Onur Tunçez and Levent Seyfi	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 4755
Adsorptive removal of methylene blue from aqueous solutions by magnetic organophilic bentonite	Abd Errahmane Zemouri, Hassina Zaghouane-Boudiaf and Ghania Bellil	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 7597
First-principles calculations of structural and electronic properties of MgCu ₂ , and MgZn ₂	Ouarda Benamara, Ahmed Boufelfel and Kamel Zanat	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	mail submission 32

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Power quality improvement based on series active power filter using fuzzy logic control scheme	ISMAIL Ghadbane, Bouzidi riad, Barkat Said	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	mail submission 33
Derin Öğrenme Teknikleri Kullanılarak Borsadaki Hisse Değerlerinin Tahmin Edilmesi	İlker Dalkıran and Mehmet Ozan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 2785
Hava Aracı Batarya Hücresinin Modellenmesi	Fatma Yıldırım Dalkıran and Sümeyra Çelik	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 4924
ÇAKŞIR OTU ÇİÇEĞİ ÖZÜTÜ İLE BİYOSENTEZLENMİŞ GÜMÜŞ NANOPARTİKÜLLERİN KARAKTERİZASYONU	Muhammed Onur Avcı and Melike Kaya Karaaslan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 5310
AN OPERATIONAL MATRIX METHOD FOR APPROXIMATE SOLUTIONS OF A CLASS OF THE SYSTEM OF THE DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS WITH DELAY-TERMS	Şuayip Yüzbaşı, Gamze Yıldırım	Turkey, Turkey	mail submission 18
AN OPERATIONAL METHOD BASED ON THE FIRST TYPE SHIFTED CHEBYSHEV POLYNOMIALS FOR SOLVING NONLINEAR LANE-EMDEN TYPE FUNCTIONAL DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS	Şuayip Yüzbaşı, Gamze Yıldırım	Turkey, Turkey	mail submission 19
APPROXIMATE SOLUTION OF THE DUFFING EQUATION BY USING FIRST BOUBAKER POLYNOMIALS	Şuayip Yüzbaşı, Gamze Yıldırım	Turkey, Turkey	mail submission 20
FERMAT COLLOCATION APPROACH FOR SOLVING THE PREDATOR-PREY SYSTEM WITH ONE DISCRETE DELAY	Şuayip Yüzbaşı, Gamze Yıldırım	Turkey, Turkey	mail submission 21
Block-Based Multi-Exposure Image Fusion Using Genetic Algorithm	Harun Akbulut and Veysel Aslantaş	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 7833
Multi-Focus Image Fusion Based on Shearlet Transform Differential Evolution Algorithm	Harun AKBULUT and Uğurcan YAŞ	Turkey, Turkey	mail submission 34

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Removal of Phenol by Electro-Fenton Process	Halima Al-Thawr, Ümran Tezcan Ün and Özlem Özden Üzmez	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 5212
Investigation of the effect on heat transfer and flow characteristics of circular impingement jets in a rectangular duct	Mehmet Gürdal	Turkey	mail submission 35
Regulation of MICA (MHC class I polypeptide-related sequence A) in Colorectal Cancer	Esra Yılmaz, Burak Küçük and Ercan Çaçan	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1078
AZ KATLI KONUT İNŞAASINDA FARKLI TAŞIYICI SİSTEMLERİN MALİYET AÇISINDAN İNCELENMESİ	Murad Khalf, Abdulhalim Karaşin and İbrahim Baran Karaşin	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	mail submission 36
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Electric Power Generation Potential Estimation and Exergy Analysis in Wind Turbines: A case study	Durukan Erdoğan, Kenan Yiğit and Bora Acarkan	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 2978
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